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TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES
732559

ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-Creation Integrated Methodology- v1

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Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

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Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
LIST OF FIGURES	4
LIST OF TABLES	4
ABSTRACT	5
1 INTRODUCTION	6
1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE.....	6
1.2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH	6
1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE.....	8
1.4 RELATION TO OTHER TOYLABS WPS AND TASKS.....	9
1.5 INSIGHTS FROM WP1	9
2 LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS	14
2.1 TOYLABS DOMAINS OF INTEREST.....	14
2.2 CO-CREATION AND OPEN INNOVATION	15
2.2.1 <i>Toy Industry’s Perspective</i>	18
2.2.2 <i>Co-Creation & Open Innovation State of the Art in Manufacturing</i>	18
2.2.3 <i>Key take-aways</i>	25
2.3 MARKET TREND ANALYSIS	25
2.3.1 <i>Traditional Market Trend Analysis Approaches in the toy industry</i>	25
2.3.2 <i>Social Network Analysis for Trends Detection & Market Understanding</i>	26
2.3.3 <i>Key take-aways</i>	48
2.4 AUGMENTED REALITY FOR FEEDBACK GATHERING.....	48
2.4.1 <i>Background</i>	48
2.4.2 <i>Landscape Review</i>	50
2.4.3 <i>Augmented Reality as part of the TOYLABS Integrated Methodology</i>	60
2.4.4 <i>Key take-aways</i>	61
2.5 PARTNER MATCHING.....	62
2.5.1 <i>Background</i>	62
2.5.2 <i>Toy Industries Perspective</i>	64
2.5.3 <i>Key take-aways</i>	69
3 TOYLABS OPEN INNOVATION AND CO-CREATION METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS	70
3.1 STAKEHOLDERS IDENTIFICATION	70
3.2 METHODOLOGY DEFINITION	73
3.2.1 <i>Introduction</i>	73
3.2.2 <i>Open Innovation and Co-creation Holistic Methodology</i>	73
3.2.3 <i>Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis Methodology</i>	82
3.2.4 <i>End-user Feedback Acquisition through Augmented Reality</i>	93
3.2.5 <i>Partner Matching and Selection Methodology</i>	97
4 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS	111
ANNEX I: REFERENCES	113
ANNEX II: PARTNER SELECTION TECHNICAL CRITERIA	120

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1-1 DELIVERABLE METHODOLOGY OUTLINE	8
FIGURE 1-2 RELATION WITH OTHER TASKS & WPS.....	9
FIGURE 2-1 TOYLABS METHODOLOGY LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS KEY TERMS.....	14
FIGURE 2-2 OPEN VS CLOSED INNOVATION MODEL.....	15
FIGURE 2-3 COLLABORATIVE PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT (BUYUKOZKAN & ARSENYAN, 2012).....	17
FIGURE 2-4 INTERVENTION OF AUGMENTED REALITY (RED POINTS IN THE FIGURE) IN THE TOYLABS HIGH LEVEL WORKFLOW PROCESS.....	60
FIGURE 2-5 OUTSOURCING ON PREPRODUCTION STAGE	65
FIGURE 2-6 OUTSOURCING ON PRODUCTION STAGE	66
FIGURE 2-7 OUTSOURCING ON MOST FREQUENT PLASTIC MANUFACTURING PROCESSES.....	67
FIGURE 2-8 OUTSOURCING ON POSTPRODUCTION STAGE.....	68
FIGURE 3-1 TOYLABS METHODOLOGY DIAGRAM.....	74
FIGURE 3-2 MARKET TRENDS AND SOCIAL FEEDBACK ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY IN STEPS.....	84
FIGURE 3-3 “AUGMENTED REALITY AS A FEEDBACK CHANNEL” DEPLOYMENT METHODOLOGY	95
FIGURE 3-4. CONSTRUCTION OF STRUCTURAL HIERARCHY	108

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1-1. COMPANIES PROFILE.	10
TABLE 1-2 TOY COMPANIES' PROFILE BASED ON DIFFERENT VARIABLES	11
TABLE 2-1 COMMON DEFINITIONS FOR CROWDSOURCING	16
TABLE 2-2 CO-CREATION & OPEN INNOVATION SOTA.....	20
TABLE 2-3 LITERATURE REVIEW FOR SOCIAL FEEDBACK AND TRENDS ANALYSIS.....	36
TABLE 2-4. COMPARISON OF AUGMENTED REALITY PLATFORMS.....	54
TABLE 3-1. STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION.....	70
TABLE 3-2. PARTNERS’ POTENTIAL INVOLVEMENT IN THE TOYLABS CO-CREATION PROCESS	99
TABLE 3-3. BLUEPRINT MODEL REQUIREMENTS.....	100
TABLE 0-1 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO 3D PRINTING	120
TABLE 0-2 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO 3D SCANNING.....	120
TABLE 0-3 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO CIRCUIT PRODUCTION	120
TABLE 0-4 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO CNC MILLING	121
TABLE 0-5 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO INKJET PRINTING	121
TABLE 0-6 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO KNITTING MACHINE	121
TABLE 0-7 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO LASER CUTTING.....	121
TABLE 0-8 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO MOULD CASTING	122
TABLE 0-9 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO SEWING MACHINE	122
TABLE 0-10 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO SOLDERING STATION	122
TABLE 0-11 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO VACUUM FORMING.....	122
TABLE 0-12 TECHNICAL CRITERIA RELATED TO VINYL CUTTING.....	123

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this deliverable is to hand over a unified methodology, to be used by the toy industry, and specifically SMEs, for attaching more value to their design processes and new product development activities. This will be achieved through the collaboration of different stakeholders, building on the notion of co-creation and open innovation that aims at accelerating their innovation cycles resulting to more inspirational, novel and desirable creations, while also partner matching functionalities will make possible to find time-wisely and effortlessly the right partner for the task in question, augmented reality will ensure the acquisition of informed and accurate end-users' feedback and finally market trend analysis will integrate crowd wisdom into new product development activities for the toy industry.

In this context, a landscape analysis was implemented in section 2 of this deliverable on the research fields of "Co-creation and Open Innovation", "Market Trend Analysis", "Augmented Reality for feedback gathering" and finally "Partner Matching", both from the perspective of the manufacturing industry in general but also zooming in the toy industry, in particular, to identify its state-of-the-art with respect to the general research community. This analysis evinced the variety and volume of ongoing research studies on these fields, but also the challenge to be met inside ToyLabs in order to turn these results towards the needs of the toy industry, thus providing a unique offering.

The valuable insights gained from this literature review were used as input for the construction of a well-defined and extendable methodological approach for renovating the design and manufacturing processes of the toy industry. Firstly, the discrete methodological steps of the holistic ToyLabs methodology under the spirit of Open Innovation were defined, while afterwards the discrete methodological foundations for market trend analysis, augmented reality for feedback gathering and partner matching were introduced. Thus, a concrete workflow was created to guide the next steps of the project and specifically the design and development of the ToyLabs platform and its added-value components.

The work done on this deliverable will be updated during the next months of the project, both with respect to the literature review and the project's methodology, and its results will be documented on a next deliverable, D2.2, in M13.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

To redesign the way that the toy industry approaches new product development through ToyLabs, a complete, well-defined and extendable methodology needs to be defined. In that view, the central questions that are to be answered, in the context of the present deliverable, have to do with “What will ToyLabs do?” and “Why is it going to do it?”. This deliverable aims to make use of the research work already done in WP1 to document the fusion of the various pieces of information, either direct or extracted and its conclusions into a coherent and easily understandable methodology and blueprint of how the various project’s goal as identified by its stakeholders requirements are going to be tackled as well as how the technical aspects of the project are to be implemented. The contents of the following chapters provide the material that is being actively encoded into technical specifications for WP3 and with them forms a contiguous feedback loop that will make the ToyLabs methodology a living document, ever enriched and evolving until it reaches a final state of maturity in its second version.

This document aims to strike a balance between the amount of in-depth analysis necessary to feed the technical requirements of the platform, and the descriptiveness needed to make its contents accessible to all other stakeholders, toy manufacturers and FabLabs, ready to accept their input, and become the basis of their understanding and continuous interaction with the ToyLabs community. In this spirit, the ToyLabs methodology will be described in steps, under the umbrella of Open Innovation, thus forming the methodological foundations, which will be able to be treated as stand-alone methodologies and to develop a workflow that merges these foundations into a holistic approach.

Based on the DoA of the ToyLabs project, this deliverable is titled “ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation Integrated Methodology-v1” and is the direct outcome of all WP2 tasks until month 6 of the project. This document will be published a second and final time in month 13 of the project, where it will be updated to incorporate all further research and further feedback from other work packages into the methodology of ToyLabs until that point.

1.2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The methodological approach by which the current deliverable takes form starts from a general perspective and focuses on defining an illustrative methodology for each of the ToyLabs main components. In the first part, the core conclusions from the Landscape Analysis are presented, starting with a study of the state-of-play on ToyLabs domains of interest, as well as the existing practices on these domains

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

concerning the toy industry, and a classification of these domains into broader categories and fields of study. These fields are specifically chosen to be leveraged as input for the clarification of the ToyLabs methodological foundations, as described in the DoA, representing distinct tasks within the project. In the second part of the analysis, these are matched to the resulting methodology, which is again separated in these components, starting with a recording of the stakeholders of the ToyLabs solution. From that point on, the stakeholders identified can be considered final and will be used in all following ToyLabs tasks and activities as the main beneficiaries of the ToyLabs solution.

Specifically, the first part deals with Open Innovation and Co-creation models from both the traditional manufactures' perspective and then from the side of the toy industry, combined with the current academic literature on the subject. From it, the Open Innovation and Co-Creation Holistic Methodology is formed. The aim of the task is to use the existing experience to find how traditional companies in the toy industry can embrace an open innovation ecosystem, by supporting them in the process, according to their specific needs.

The second part deals with Market Trend analysis. To capture the landscape in this area, both the specific state-of-the-art practices to extract market trends in the toy industry are documented, as well the current state of the field of Social Network Analysis for trends detection and feedback management. These are combined in the following chapter to form the Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis methodology, answering the question of how the Social Web can be incorporated indirectly into new product development processes, serving as useful information source to capture underlying trends in toy industry's specific domains (e.g. dolls, puzzles etc.) as well as the sentiment of the social media users talking about these topics.

The third part refers to the use of Augmented Reality (AR) for end-user feedback collection. The current academic literature and commercial approaches are initially documented and considered in order to derive the optimal methodology to introduce the use of Mixed and Augmented Reality to gather end-user feedback, taking into consideration the particularities of the toy industry, and especially the considerations applicable to the SME toy manufacturers.

Lastly, the fourth part refers to the partner matching and selection methodology, starting from documenting the methods that are currently employed in the industry to find and select partners and sub-contractors, the range of criteria and priorities used to do so, and transitioning to the description of the Partner Matching and Selection Methodology for ToyLabs as well as the reasoning behind it.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Figure 1-1 Deliverable Methodology Outline

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The structure of the document is as follows:

Chapter 1 introduces this document, in which the purpose and scope of the deliverable at hand, the methodological approach of the research done to achieve this result, its current structure, the relation of this deliverable and its tasks to other work packages and tasks and the insights from WP1 are documented.

Chapter 2 is the Landscape Analysis performed to create the ToyLabs methodology. It starts with the identification of the ToyLabs domains of interest that will be examined in the following subsections as part of this chapter and continues with four main scientific fields, that of Co-creation and Open Innovation, Market Trend Analysis, Augmented Reality for feedback gathering and Partner Matching, that are being researched both from a more general perspective as well as zooming in the toy industry if relevant, remarkable work or application examples can be found there for each of the above mentioned domains.

Chapter 3 contains the methodological foundations on which the ToyLabs project and platform are based. It starts with the identification of the key stakeholders and then it defines the methodology, as a matter of discrete and successive steps, starting with the ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation methodology, the Market Trends and Social Feedback methodology, End-User Feedback Acquisition through Augmented Reality methodology and finally the ToyLabs methodology for Partner Matching.

Chapter 4 documents the main conclusions of the deliverable at hand, as well as a brief report on the next steps to be taken in the project with respect to WP2 activities.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

1.4 RELATION TO OTHER TOYLABS WPS AND TASKS

To derive this deliverable, the research made draws significantly from the work done in WP1 – Requirements Engineering and Validation Framework. The theoretical foundations built on the tasks T1.1 - ToyLabs Innovations Exploration and Approach Justification and T1.2 – Project Positioning in the Toy Industry Business Landscape is a central source on which the Landscape Analysis is based on. Combined, D1.1- Exploring Progress and Innovation in ToyLabs Tackled Domains and ToyLabs Concept Definition- v1, is the theoretical background for Chapter 2 of this deliverable.

The other two tasks from WP1, T1.3 - Stakeholders Requirements and High-level Usage Scenarios and T1.4 - ToyLabs Validation and Impact Measurement Framework are providing the usage scenarios from the project’s stakeholders. Expanding on this, the deliverable D1.2- Stakeholders’ Requirements Identification and Validation Framework Determination- v1, as well as the work done in the four WP2 tasks to form the Landscape Analysis, are the basis of Chapter 3 in this deliverable.

In this context, the ToyLabs Methodology is delivered to WP3 - ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development. This deliverable feeds the task T3.1- Technology Requirements and ToyLabs Components Analysis, where, using, in part, the equivalent sections from Chapter 3 of the current deliverable, the specific technical requirements are generated.

Figure 1-2 Relation with other Tasks & WPs

1.5 INSIGHTS FROM WP1

Useful insights from WP1 are detected stemming from a qualitative exploratory research and an in-depth analysis of toy manufacturing processes and needs, implemented and documented in the context of D1.1. These insights are being collected here in order to be considered as a starting point to proceed for the work to be done in this deliverable.

The key take-aways of D1.1 can be outlined in the following points:

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- **Production is outsourced**

Most of the manufacturing processes involved in manufacturing toys in Europe and transforming materials are performed by an outsourced company, instead of by the company itself, in-house. This fact means that European toy companies are more focused on the conceptual design, detailed design production, and the delivery phases, than on the production phase. They can be considered more as “commercial” than “industrial” companies.

- **Relocation of the industry**

The location of toy manufacturing processes has experienced great changes in the last few decades. The process is changing continuously, and in recent years it can be observed that some companies have been outsourcing the processes related to engineering to Asian countries, taking advantage of the proximity of two areas that are directly connected by land. The evolution of this trend in the coming decades is certainly unpredictable. Some experts suggest that a technological revolution and an increase in transport costs (e.g., by adding a pollution tax) could reverse the process and manufacturing could return to European countries. On the other hand, some experts suggest that there is a considerable possibility that design activities will be outsourced to Asia in coming years.

- **Immersion phase before design is not performed by SMEs**

Time and resources assigned to the immersion phase are very different between big companies and SMEs. This activity should be performed by SMEs, but many of them do not do so. This fact implies that small companies very often begin the activity of generating ideas with an inadequate level of information and knowledge about markets, consumer insights and trends. Toys marketing departments should provide the necessary information to toy designers before the generation of new ideas, and not be limited to adding their value once the products have been designed.

- **Absence of historical data hindering innovation**

One of the main barriers for innovation in the toy industry is the absence of historical data for this type of products. The toy sector bases most of their forecasting and decision making on this type of data.

As far as the **toy companies’ profile** is concerned, a categorisation of them based on certain main variables that define a toy company’s profile has been undertaken in D1.1 and is presented in the table that follows.

Table 1-1. Companies profile.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Table 1-2 Toy companies' profile based on different variables

VARIABLE	COMPANY PROFILE	DESCRIPTION
Manufacturing processes	Industrial	An industrial company is the type of company that carries out all the manufacturing processes internally.
	Commercial	This type of company is related to the outsourcing of manufacturing processes to Asia and/ or other countries, one of the major changes in the toy industry in the last decade. Commercial companies usually focus all their efforts on design and marketing processes and they usually outsource manufacturing.
Turnover	Micro and Small	Small and micro companies have a turnover of less than 10 million, and have less than 50 employees. A special type of company in this group are Start-ups.
	Medium and Large	Medium and large companies have a turnover of more than 10 million, and have more than 50 employees.
Core activity	Manufacturers	The main activity of this type of company is to design, engineer and sometimes produce toys.
	Distributors	In the last few decades, distributors have increased the number of products they sell that are their own brand. Usually, this type of company buys finished toys, but there are some examples of distributors that also undertake the design stage tasks, e.g., Imaginarium.
Internationalisation process	Local	This type of company sells most of their toys in their own country.
	Global	This type of company sells its toys in different countries and continents. Normally, this type of company has offices in different parts of the world.
Value proposition	Physical products	This type of company focuses its activity on the creation of new toys.

VARIABLE	COMPANY PROFILE	DESCRIPTION
	Content generators	These companies have evolved from toy companies to media companies: TV series and films are a core activity for them, engaging children and then selling toys.
Toy value	Educational	All toys have an educational value, but for these companies this variable is the main reason for creating a new toy. They sell toys to families and to schools/ teachers, usually through educational channels. These companies brand their products as specialty toys.
	Commercial	Usually this type of toys is made for enjoyment and entertainment. Even if they have some educational value, the focus is on fun. These companies brand their products as toys.
Toy technology	High level of technology	Technology has had a great influence on the toy industry in recent decades, and some companies see technology as their main strategy of differentiation, by adding technology to their products when the technology is matured enough, and their price range is reasonable for a toy. Clear examples of this type of toys are: robots, electronic pets, drones, etc.
	Low level of technology	This type of company normally does not add technology to their products because they do not have the knowhow or resources required, or because they believe that children are overwhelmed with technology and choose a more traditional approach.

According to the results of the research as well as the questionnaires that were shared to toy manufacturing companies, the most important manufacturing processes for these companies are the following:

- Certification and laboratory
- Generation of new ideas, new concepts definitions and product design
- Supplier management (creation of supplier/experts contact lists certified by ToyLabs), raw materials and components purchase
- Costs analysis and price strategy
- Quality control (especially when communicating with outsourced companies)
- Half-finishing manufacturing and assembly
- Sales analysis, market evolution, user feedback and user assistance

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- Transport and logistics

Furthermore, as far as the contribution of ToyLabs in these companies is concerned, it was concluded that ToyLabs offering should not be limited to the production of toys, but instead be extended to the whole process of toy creation; from its ideation until its sale.

In particular, areas where toy companies would mostly value the support of ToyLabs are:

- User test, user feedback, market evolution and product placement
- Certification and laboratory
- Raw materials and components purchasing
- Prototype development
- Product design
- Idea generation and concept definition
- Advertising

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2 LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

2.1 TOYLABS DOMAINS OF INTEREST

The ToyLabs Methodology focuses its efforts into creating a co-creation and Open Innovation platform on a specific number of scientific domains that it aims to interrelate. In this Landscape Analysis, these domains are thoroughly studied separately and provide the basis on which the methodology that follows in the next chapter of the current deliverable will be built. This state-of-the-art analysis that is implemented in the following sections aims to come up with certain conclusions that will guide the ToyLabs methodology development ensuring maximisation of the impact that ToyLabs envisions for the SME toy industry.

In Figure 2-1 some of the main terms used for the landscape analysis are presented. The **foundation** on which the methodology is based on consists of the joint domains of co-creation and Open Innovation. This domain is the central focus point of the project and the resulting platform as a whole. The **enabler**, however, of the co-creation process is the Partner Matching domain, which is used to support Open Innovation and set up the process of co-creation. Lastly, the Augmented Reality for **feedback** gathering and the Market Trend Analysis are two domains that are studied to infuse **Added Value** into ToyLabs, and be used as tools to enhance extroversion and creativity towards the real market's needs and to enrich the co-creation interactions with useful information in various steps of the toy development process.

Figure 2-1 ToyLabs Methodology Landscape Analysis key terms

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.2 CO-CREATION AND OPEN INNOVATION

Starting with the definition of the term of “**Open Innovation**”, two different (but not mutually exclusive) research streams can be identified in the academic literature and these streams are mainly represented by Henry Chesbrough and Eric von Hippel as follows:

- The first definition was developed by Henry Chesbrough and it encourages companies to acquire outside sources of innovation to improve product lines and shorten the time required to bring products to market or release internally developed innovation which does not fit the company's business model but could be effectively used elsewhere.¹
- The second stream follows Eric von Hippel who translates open innovation as users' collaboration to develop innovations in a virtual environment, thus taking a user and tool perspective. Von Hippel's view is represented by the users of an OIP, i.e. the innovators, and the focus is given on IT-based tools for open innovation. (Hallerstede, 2013)

Figure 2-2 Open vs Closed Innovation Model

Traditionally, companies and organisations used to view innovation as something that should be handled exclusively inside the company with extreme secrecy because they used to view it as a competitive advantage. However, as shown in the above figure “open innovation creates an environment where individuals and organisations can actively get involved in the creation of mutually beneficial solutions².” That means

¹ <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/open-innovation.html>

² <https://www.wazoku.com/open-innovation-vs-crowdsourcing-vs-co-creation/>

that companies that adopt this model innovate with the help of the wider community of the company (i.e. customers, suppliers, distributors etc.). Consequently, open innovation is an inclusive, social way of solving complex issues and improving processes.³

One important division of open innovation is called crowdsourcing and it is of specific interest in the scope of the ToyLabs project. In general, crowdsourcing etymologically is formed from the two words: crowd, referring to the people participating in an initiative, and sourcing, making reference to all practices aimed at finding, evaluating and engaging suppliers of goods and services (Estelles-Arolas & Gonzalez-Ladron-de-Guevara, 2012). Certain existing and most commonly encountered in the literature definitions of crowdsourcing are presented in the table below.

Table 2-1 Common definitions for Crowdsourcing

Definitions	Sources
“The act of taking a job traditionally performed by a designated agent (usually an employee) and outsourcing it to an undefined, generally large group of people in the form of an open call.”	(Howe, 2008)
“A strategic model to attract an interested, motivated crowd of individuals capable of providing solutions superior in quality and quantity to those that even traditional forms of business can.”	(Brabham, 2008)
“New online distributed problem-solving and production model in which networked people collaborate to complete a task.”	(Vuković, 2009)
“The opening of the innovation process of a firm to integrate numerous and disseminated outside competencies through web facilities”. These competencies can be those of individuals (for example creative people, scientists, engineers) or existing organised communities (for example open source software communities).	(Chanal, 2008)

³ <https://www.wazoku.com/open-innovation-vs-crowdsourcing-vs-co-creation/>

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

With respect to **Co-Creation**, co-creation is nowadays a widely adopted process and thus many researchers have tried to give their own definition to explain it. Two indicative definitions about the concept of Co-Creation can be seen below:

- Co-Creation is a business strategy focusing on customer experience and interactive relationships. Co-creation allows and encourages a more active involvement from the customer to create a value rich experience.⁴
- Co-creation, unlike traditional company-driven concepts of marketing, is about the joint creation of value by a company and other stakeholders, and in particular consumers who work with the company to co-construct the service experience to suit his or her preferences (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004a).

Co-Creation is a broad concept that manifests in various facets of today's business environment. In the scope of the ToyLabs project, we will focus on **co-creation in new product development** that is also known as **Collaborative Product Development (CPD)**. It was explained in D1.1: Exploring Progress and Innovation in ToyLabs Tackled Domains and ToyLabs Concept Definition, that Collaborative Product Development is "a technology-centered process including two or more partners with diverse competence, experience, culture, skill and location joining complementary resources to design/develop new/innovative/improved products in order to gain competitive advantage, innovate, explore new markets, share risks and costs and accelerate PD process." (Buyukozkan & Arsenyan, 2012). The visualisation of this definition is shown in the following figure.

Figure 2-3 Collaborative product Development (Buyukozkan & Arsenyan, 2012)

⁴ <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/co-creation.html>

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.2.1 Toy Industry's Perspective

The emergence of collaborative design is changing the landscape of the practice of design by allowing the creation of new domains of collective creativity.

Co-design is defined by joining the creativity of designers into groups of people who have different profiles and work together in the process of the elaboration of the design⁵. Co-creation puts the tools for communication and creativity in the hands of the people who will directly benefit from the results.

The collaboration of users during the creation of a product happens normally more in the validation phase. These validations can be carried out in all the stages, but normally is done to test concepts and prototypes. When users participate, the techniques followed are focused on groups and interviews. Users give their opinion and propose ideas to improve the products. These activities allow companies to detect problems and ideas to solve them.

Other practices to develop new ideas or improve existing ones are to carry out co-creation workshops. These are creative and social sessions based on collaboration between producers and users. To create a co-creative atmosphere, some of the techniques used are brainstorming, mindmapping, role-playing, rapid prototyping or other activities to get the group engaged in the challenge to be tackled.

Based on the results of the interviews with companies, it can be concluded that co-creation workshops are gradually becoming more popular in toy companies. Nevertheless, SME toy companies are not highly involved in them when developing new product concepts.

2.2.2 Co-Creation & Open Innovation State of the Art in Manufacturing

This sub-chapter includes the SotA analysis of manufacturing platforms that are heavily based in the concepts of Co-Creation and Open Innovation to solve current problems and shortcomings in the manufacturing industry. To better cite the reviewed approaches, a reporting schema is developed and applied. A set of appropriate criteria/ features relevant to other collaboration platforms are identified and described below:

- **Paper Title:** encompassing all the basic information for the mentioned papers such as title and URL.
- **Platform Name:** the name of the platform/ framework that was developed in the context of each paper
- **General Topic:** this column will describe the general topic of the paper under study. The possible values considered to cover the spectrum of the papers

⁵ Sanders, E., Stappers, P. (2008); "Co-creation and the new landscapes of design"; CoDesign; Taylor & Francis, submitted for publication.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

under analysis are: Open Innovation and Co-Creation. Finally, it must be clarified that these two values are not mutually exclusive.

- **Description:** comprising a one-line description of what the approach/methodology/ application under analysis is aiming at developing.
- **Application Area:** utilised to indicate the scientific and application areas of the reported approach. The goal of this facet is to go to a further depth from the “General Topic” facet and identify these core scientific/application areas which the paper under study is dealing with. As a result, the two main possible values of this column are Collaborative Product Development and Crowdsourcing.
- **Target Group:** if the paper under study indicates a specific target group that is aimed to take advantage of the paper’s results, it will be mentioned here. Possible values can be SMEs, Companies, Factories, Organisations etc.
- **Co-Creation Participants:** this field will describe the different stakeholder categories that participate in the Co-Creation procedure of a manufacturing platform, provided that the platform under study includes such a function.
- **Benefits:** this field will contain qualitative benefits drawn from the framework/platform under question. The purpose of this column is to show how the concepts of Co-Creation and Open Innovation can add value in a manufacturing procedure.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

Table 2-2 Co-Creation & Open Innovation SOTA

Paper Title	Platform Name	General topic	Description	Application Area	Target Group	Co-Creation Participants	Benefits
Design, programming and orchestration of heterogeneous manufacturing systems through VR-powered remote collaboration (Galambos et al., 2015)	VirCA	Co-Creation	A platform is developed to act as a communication medium among different stakeholders through the use of virtual/augmented reality in order to solve the problems that arise from modern manufacturing	Collaborative Product Development, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Remote laboratories, industries, universities	End-Users, Researchers, Developers, Engineers	Enables sharing manufacturing equipment for remote collaboration. Allows for increasingly sophisticated bidirectional data exchange between VirCA and third-party physical devices. Allows flexible interconnection of virtual test production lines, allowing for thorough testing.
An interoperable solution for Cloud manufacturing (Vincent Wang & Xu, 2013)	ICMS	Co-Creation	In order to take advantage of emerging state-of-the-art approaches, relevant to cloud manufacturing the ICMS platform is developed to enable remote collaboration and interaction among stakeholders in a collaborative manufacturing environment.	Collaborative Product Development, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	SMEs, Manufacturing Enterprises	Customer Users, Enterprise Users	Traverses all the possible paths and finds the most sufficient solution in terms of time. Makes it possible to realise remote collaboration, coordination, and interaction among participants. Provides data interoperability, customised service and better enterprise performance.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

A Web-Based Platform for Collaborative Product Design, Review and Evaluation (Mavrikios et al., 2011)	CPD	Co-Creation	A new system is developed to serve as a multiuser real-time collaboration tool for distributed and collaborative product development activities, focusing on SMEs that cannot afford such sophisticated tools.	Collaborative Product Development, Partner Matching	SMEs, Manufacturing Industries	Designers, Engineers, managers, Suppliers, Customers	Provides a variety of functionalities for real-time collaboration during design activities. Online interactive review for evaluation purposes. Has flexible, modular architecture, easy to be used and extended. Can be used for a wide range of products. Consequently it is an appropriate tool for SMEs that cannot afford sophisticated tools.
Development of a web-based collaboration platform for manufacturing product and process design evaluation using virtual reality techniques (Pappas, Karabatsou, Mavrikios, & Chryssolouris, 2006)	DiCoDEv	Co-Creation	A new platform is developed that enables multiple users to collaboratively work in the same project in real time. The innovation concept of this platform lies in the use of virtual reality (VR) technology	Collaborative Product Development	Manufacturing Industries	End-users, Designers, Manufacturers	Allows multiple users to work in a collaborative way. Leads to more efficient evaluation of a design using digital human simulation. Provides quick and easy product data storage and decision support for evaluating alternative designs.
Collaborative Product Development and	WEBCD MC	Co-Creation	A platform-based strategy and approach is presented for	Collaborative Product Development	Manufacturing Companies	Designers of cooperating companies,	Designers in different teams and organisations may participate and collaborate in the design

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

Customization: A Platform-Based Strategy and Implementation (Zha & Sriram, 2004)			collaborative product development and customization.			Customers, Manufacturing Engineers	process (Zha, Sriram 2004). Provides chat functions so that designers can communicate with each other during the design process.
Collaborating to create: The Internet as a platform for customer engagement in product innovation (Sawhney, Verona, & Prandelli, 2005)	NA	Collaboration in Product Innovation	An exploratory approach is deployed where internet-based collaboration mechanisms to the NPD process are studied and patterns and implications are derived	New Product Development	Companies	Customers	The proposed approach allows firms to explore new frontiers in co-creation of value. Allows firms to engage customers more broadly, more richly, and more speedily. The firm can access knowledge at low cost from individual customers and it is not constrained by geographical barriers
Crowdsourcing new product ideas over time: An analysis of the Dell IdeaStorm community (Bayus, 2012)	Dell IdeaStorm	Crowdsourcing for Ideation	The purpose of the paper is to highlight some of the challenges in maintaining an ongoing supply of quality ideas from the crowd over time.	Crowdsourcing Communities, New Product Development	Companies	Consumers, Serial Ideators	The paper highlights some of the difficulties in maintaining an ongoing supply of quality ideas from the crowd over time and emphasises the need for more research on crowdsourcing communities, thus pointing the research community in the right direction.
Open Innovation with Customers:	Threadless.com	Crowdsourcing for Ideation	Describes Threadless paradigm and	New Product Development, Customer Co-	Manufacturing industry with possible	Customers, External Experts	Threadless' approach doesn't require huge research budgets or

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

Crowdsourcing and Co-Creation at Threadless (Piller, 2010)			how its “crowdsourcing” approach works and what the factors of its success are. The paper also comments briefly on idea to transfer the Threadless model onto other industries.	creation, Ideation	fit to other industries		creative brilliance. It has tapped into a fundamental economic shift, a movement away from passive consumerism. Threadless' user community numbers over a million users by offering incentives to designers and customers whose design gets made into a shirt.
The role of technology in the shift towards open innovation: the case of Procter & Gamble (Dodgson, Gann, & Salter, 2006)	Procter and Gamble's Connect and Develop strategy	Open Innovation	New technologies, called Innovation Technology (IvT) can be used to reshape the innovation process and the ways knowledge is constructed, shared and used	Collaborative Product Development	Not indicated	NA	The case study shows that a suite of new technologies for data mining, simulation, prototyping and visual representation, (what we call ‘innovation technology’), helps to support open innovation in Procter and Gamble.
Toolkits for idea competitions: A novel method to integrate users in new product development (Piller & Walcher, 2006)	Adidas toolkits	Open Innovation	Development of Internet-based toolkits for idea competitions (TIC) for user integration in New Product Development (NPD)	Idea Competition, New Product Development	Companies	Customers	High willingness of customers to participate with high creativity according to the CAT system. The majority (80%) of the contributions can be seen as suggestions for improvements concerning the current offerings of Adidas.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

							Adidas' management was very satisfied with the quality of the submissions in general, and rather enthusiastic about the winning ideas. Two of them are presently in the state of implementation.
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Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.2.3 Key take-aways

In general, it can be concluded that, although co-creation and open innovation in the toy industry is currently limited, especially with regard to SMEs, and is usually appeared through the creation of dedicated co-creation workshops, an unprecedented opportunity emerges to co-create and open innovate using online tools and platforms, thus overcoming distance and location limitations (a barrier strongly applying on SMEs), while privacy respecting rules and anonymisation functionalities ensure free expression of ideas.

2.3 MARKET TREND ANALYSIS

Market trend detection and analysis in the business sector is included in the context of business intelligence, in the sense that it enables identification of opportunities and decision making about them.

Trends are the directions towards which something tends to move or change. Related to the market, trends give information about how a society and the industrial sectors are adapting to a great variety of variables that are in constant evolution. These changes define the behaviours of consumers and companies in aspects that are relevant to the development and distribution of products and services.

Detecting these changes, knowing their reasons and knowing what implications they will have for companies will prepare the industry to anticipate changes, adapt to them and even be able to generate them, manage them and boost them.

2.3.1 Traditional Market Trend Analysis Approaches in the toy industry

In the toy industry, as is also the case in the manufacturing sector in general, in order to carry out trend research there are various requirements and methodologies that need to be considered. There are two main requirements that should be taken into account before starting to generate any trend research:

- *A historical review, retrospective knowledge.* Knowledge about the past is needed to envision the future. The past helps researchers on trend analysis understand the evolution of this field and the reasons behind what happened. In the same way, to comprehend the values and behaviours of new families, the researchers need to understand how they have changed throughout the centuries.
- *A multidisciplinary team.* The team of researchers on trend analysis should be composed of experts in various fields related to marketing, sociology, anthropology, design, child psychology, engineering, etc. Trend Analysis is a complex field of study that requires different points of view and expertise.

Some of the main phases for extracting market trends are as follows:

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- **Information Collection.** A great amount of information from different sources should first be collected and organised to analyse market and social trends. The methodologies used are desk research and observation. Regarding desk research, there are various ways to gather data such as news, magazines, books, scientific research, catalogues and websites or social networks and other online resources. Regarding observation, the most important activities are: visits to fairs, distribution visits and city visits.
- **Analysis and definition of trends.** Trend specialists are trained to analyse and organise a lot of information in a way that can lead to conclusions. In this phase of the research, there are multiple meetings with the multidisciplinary team. These sessions are focused on looking for patterns that point towards specific directions. Some of the techniques that support this phase are: affinity diagrams, mind maps or positioning maps. After the trends have been determined, another relevant matter is to give them a name; usually a word that summarises the main ideas behind them.

2.3.2 Social Network Analysis for Trends Detection & Market Understanding

2.3.2.1 *Background*

The previous section outlined the traditional approach, applied also in the toy industry, for market trend detection and analysis. This approach, although really necessary in every business activity, have the significant disadvantage of being time consuming (e.g. desk research is an inherently time consuming activity), while it is very likely that the background and behaviour of the sample (as a result of observation activities) at that time are being passed into the results, influencing the analysis and introducing a bias into them (Ohana & Tierney, 2009).

Technology provides a solution to this challenge detected for the business sector since it allows access to the vast amount of information available on the internet, where a significant number of individuals express their opinions freely. In this context, feedback may be given even when not directly asked for through various social networks where users express their sentiments and opinions towards almost everything, including products and services for which they want to share and exchange their experiences with other consumers. From dedicated review platforms, generic chatting sites and blog posts to crowdsourcing and ideation platforms, there is a great opportunity to extract valuable information revealing what consumers dislike, like or even desire. Therefore, it is evident that an alternative path to the traditional approach for market trends detection and analysis emerges, while the amount of generated data calls for advanced approaches and methodologies, since manual processing is generally not an option.

As regards the online resources from which useful content about consumer preferences and current trends in a topic or industry can be extracted, all Web 2.0 applications where users are freely expressing themselves by creating content on the web (user-generated content) can be considered. A swarm of web and mobile

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

applications, including social media platforms, blogs and forums, e-shops and other websites for product reviews enable the envisioned role of Web 2.0 as a medium that leverages user participation and openness. Users use the provided Web 2.0 channels as a means to communicate and share not only facts and news, but their personal opinions and feelings, as well. Dedicated websites for reviews of products-services commonly found in e-shops are an obvious source of information that could be exploited by manufacturers in order to identify products flaws and benefits as perceived by their customers. However, the expression of personal thoughts is not limited to such targeted platforms. A research by (Davis & Khazanchi, 2008) showed that the interactions among electronic Word of Mouth postings in the various social networks talking about a specific product category were statistically significant in explaining changes in product sales. In a very interesting, past research, (Jansen & Zhang, 2009) indicated that the percentage of tweets that mention brands and organisations is, impressingly, 19% over the total tweets made each day, revealing a new opportunity for the business sector. It is, thus, evident that the internet and social web behaviour of consumers provides an unprecedented source of information to be used in many areas of business intelligence, including trends detection. Gaining insights into this collective sentiment offers a competitive advantage to any company that can devote the time and money to mine these data and extract knowledge.

Interest of both academics and businesses confirms the importance of these sources of information, while focus seems to be given on analysing data from social media as the primary source of user-generated content. This is due to their wide and growing use as a means of expressing opinions, preferences and emotions, as a means of interaction and influence among users, as well as a means of promotion and targeted advertising from the companies' perspective. Undoubtedly, social media heavily contribute in enriching and republishing the already vast amounts of information available online. It is indicative to report that around 6 billion photos are uploaded every month to Facebook, every five months the total of blog posts doubles, many videos are uploaded every minute to YouTube, and there are almost half a billion daily tweets on Twitter.

Despite this great opportunity that social media are offering, great challenges also arise stemming from the great unevenness and dispersion that social media showcase. Many different types of social media exist, ranging from social networking (e.g. Facebook or LinkedIn), microblogging (Twitter), photo sharing (e.g. Flickr or Photobucket), news aggregation (e.g. Google reader, StumbleUpon, or Feedburner), video sharing (e.g. YouTube, MetaCafe or vimeo), instant messaging (e.g. Skype, or Yahoo! messenger), etc. It, thus, becomes apparent that different social networks call for differentiated processing, while also depending on the market sector as well as the topic or product / service category, the focus to be given on each social network differs, so different weighting should be considered when analysing content from different sources.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Along the above lines, social media analysis (also met as social network analysis) constitutes a vivid field of activity in the last decade, both from the research and from the business point of view. There is a great variety of definitions for social media analysis, where terms such as text mining, sentiment analysis profiling and social search are considered as subcategories under the umbrella of social media analysis; a fact that renders this field particularly wide concerning the end-to-end lifecycle of (social) data identification, acquisition, processing and analysis.

In this context, identification of trends is also introduced as an opportunity emerging from social media analysis through discovery of patterns, relationships and hidden correlations. Fields like computer science and statistics have been actively engaged in the recent years in the process of identifying trends/ trending topics and, more specifically, utilising them in order to predict the future.

Regarding trends definition, (Budak, Agrawal, & Abbadi, 2011) define trends as the frequently mentioned topics throughout the stream of user activities. (Kontostathis, Galitsky, Pottenger, Roy, & Phelps, 2004), on the other hand, define an “emerging trend” as “a topic area that is growing in interest and utility over time”. Many more definitions of the term can be found in the academic literature, while it becomes apparent that the concept of trends is particularly broad.

At this point it would be useful to make a distinction among trend detection and trend prediction. For businesses, useful insights can be gained from online sources in two dimensions. On the one part current trends and feedback gathering may give to a company the opportunity to understand their brand perception, their competitors’ power, as well as the current status of consumers’ preferences for their industry and therefore make decisions accordingly. On the other part, early identification of upcoming trends in a specified industry – before they are even known and adopted by the general public- might give an unprecedented competitive advantage to a company that would harness them on time for their benefit. However, this case is not always feasible or it involves high margins of error. On such cases, trends are useful to be detected early enough, i.e. between their start and their peak response, rather than deferred. In that view, trend detection, referring to the first dimension, and trend prediction, referring to the second, are widely researched by the academic community, but they also call, in most cases, for differentiated approaches/methodologies.

At this first iteration of the present deliverable, research as well as the methodology that follows (section 3.3.3) will mostly focus on **feedback analysis and trend detection** from social media sources, but a reference on recent trend prediction approaches would be useful to highlight certain differences that emerge. In that view, a way of approaching the issue of predicting trends in social media rather than simply detecting them has been proposed by (Saez-Trumper, Comarela, Almeida, Baeza-Yates, & Benevenuto, 2012). The paper introduces a new term to describe the people who adopt and disseminate an idea/trend before this idea actually becomes a trend, the trendsetters, distinguishing them from the influencers, who are defined as the

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

people who adopt the trend late but spread it even further and affect a large number of users. (Han, Fang, & Jia, 2014) also developed a method of predicting trends in social media taking into account, among other things, the geographical factor. Their method is based on principles of machine learning and can be applied in two cases: a) The monitoring of the propagation of a subject in the medium (spreading trace), which can be represented as a set of nodes, keywords and time stamps, predicting the future status of the given subject and b) The prediction of a subject that will likely have a great influence/impact in the future, through calculation of the evolution of a candidate time series. Finally, another recent method introduced by (Dang, Gao, & Zhou, 2016) deals with early detection of emerging topics in micro-blogging networks and is based on DBN (Dynamic Bayesian Networks) calculating the likelihood of a keyword being a trending one and then, based on the correlation between keywords, the DBSCAN algorithm is being applied to group trending keywords on trending topics. Particular mention has to be made to the time perspective, which has also been dealt with indirectly along the previous lines. Real-time detection, i.e. the task of detecting the mentions of a breaking story as close as possible in time to its first mention, require from the system identification of the theme/ story in a matter of few minutes from its first mention. However, obvious limitations in the identification of events are posed, starting from the fact that multiple terms may refer to the same event and this is something difficult to be captured (Zanzotto, Pennacchiotti, & Tsioutsoulouklis, 2011). Thus, when the time perspective is not critical (e.g. trends or topics that occur with a significant proportion in the data) better results are envisioned.

Talking about social media trends, specific reference has to be made in Twitter. In this specific social network, trends are typically driven by emerging events, breaking news and general topics that attract the attention of a large fraction of Twitter users (Mathioudakis & Koudas, 2010a). The operation model of Twitter itself is offering some trends' identification and reporting functionalities, since trending topics in the user's community or globally are being presented to him even from the social network's landing page. Trends' identification in Twitter is facilitated through the use of hashtags; when the symbol “#” is put in front of a specific term, it makes it easily discoverable and replicable by other Twitter users. Other popular social networks (e.g. Facebook) have also adopted this approach.

2.3.2.2 *Social Feedback and Trends Detection Processes*

Despite the fact that there is not a strict way to define what a trend is and what is not, as well as the fact that a trend is inherently changing, it is necessary to find an approach to model the problem of trend identification in a way that will render trends easily detectable by specialised methods throughout the large volume of web data. Although, there are such approaches in the academic literature, they are not univocal, but they differ in order to be adjusted on each specific application area. Most common applications that track trends usually use a keyword-based approach, and provide output in the form of simple terms, hashtags or term n-grams (Lau, Collier, & Baldwin,

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2012). Many developed algorithms exploit the (so-called) hidden Markov models (Stieglitz & Dang-Xuan, 2013); these models are utilised to train topic observation mechanisms, which are stored for future predictions. Another approach enhances the aforementioned one by utilising the network's topology (Budak et al., 2011). The trends are divided in two main clusters, called coordinated and uncoordinated trends that detect topics that are popular among highly clustered and distributed users, respectively. Dictionaries and/ or vocabularies are also utilised in some approaches in order to facilitate learning-based frameworks for detecting emerging topics in social media and related streams (Kasiviswanathan, Melville, Banerjee, & Sindhvani, 2011). The proposed framework consisted of two stages: determining novel documents in the stream, and subsequently identifying cluster structure among the novel documents.

In this context, a thorough and complete vision on the existing approaches/ methodologies of application of trend detection and analysis from online sources took place in the context of the present deliverable, in the form of extensive desk research on general search engines and search engines oriented towards academia and/ or research (e.g. Scopus, Google Scholar etc.). In order to effectively study the available literature, the following considerations were taken into account while reviewing the available literature and selecting the papers to be in-depth analysed in this deliverable:

- a) *Research significance*, in the sense that citation count is considered indicative of the work's importance in the domain from an academic perspective. Therefore, the ones with the larger citation count are selected for detailed review and
- b) *Latest approaches*: In order to account for the fact that older publications are possibly favoured by the choice of citation count as significance criterion, a separate search had to be made for each year since 2014 and the publications with the largest citation count per year were firstly examined and included in the research analysis.

From the results that arose, careful selection had to be realised in order to identify research approaches that fit well in the ToyLabs needs, providing an example of application or a methodology for the application of the proposed approach. The goal was to gain useful insights into prevailing approaches/methodologies for the creation of a solid ToyLabs methodology about Social Feedback and Trends analysis in the scope of manufacturing and specifically the toy industry.

Towards this end, and after the literature review, an effort was made in the context of the present deliverable to capture certain common steps and workflows that the approaches studied follow in order to document the differences that appear among them in a more structured and manageable way, that will support the reader in understanding the main points of differentiation.

Five steps were identified that is an effort to group certain processes that are commonly met in the bibliography under a broader "umbrella". These steps will

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

afterwards guide the methodology to be defined in the following chapter, in section 3.2.3.

1) **Data Collection:** Web data extraction is an important research field that has been approached with a variety of tools and is applied on multiple occasions. It constitutes a prerequisite for extracting knowledge from data, and hence a prerequisite for data mining and trend detection. This is, also because, in the most common case, there is no preexisting dataset to be processed and analysed.

Web Data Extraction Systems are a broad category of software applications that aim at collecting data from one or more web sources. The system interacts with the source and extracts data from it according to the specific needs. For example, for an HTML page, the content to be exported may be some of the elements on the page or the entire text contained therein. In the case of social networks, it may be the text of posts itself containing certain specific words or hashtags or posts that meet certain requirements (e.g., a minimum number of broadcasts, such as retweets, a specific time or geographical characteristic, etc.).

The following basic data collection cases are being distinguished:

- Through the use of a web crawler, a web spider or a web parser;
- Through the use of a search query or a simple algorithm directly at the social media programming interfaces (e.g. Twitter API, Facebook API, Sina API).

2) **Data Processing:** As a second step in the process of identifying trends, processing or pre-processing of collected data can be considered as a necessary step in any knowledge extraction processes in order to prepare the data for further analysis. This may mean "cleaning" or filtering the data and processing them to obtain a single form on which the more specialised algorithms that follow to detect topics or other complex process can work efficiently. Data that are being extracted in the previous steps are predominantly on natural language, therefore they call for Natural Language processing methodologies.

In the context of this step, two categories of processing are being considered to group the methodologies frequently applied to acquire a curated form of data to serve as input in the algorithms that follow:

- a) Linguistic data processing (e.g. stop-words removal, POS tagging, etc.) and
- b) Filtering based on the needs of each specific case (e.g. emoticons removal, blocking of past posts based on time criteria, etc.).

More information on these two categories will be given in the Methodology chapter (i.e. section 3.2.3) where specific NLP techniques and filtering processes will be considered and explained.

3) **Topic Detection:** Topic detection along with trend detection, which is the next step, are the two core steps in a trend detection methodology. They can also be considered as one step, in cases where the algorithms considered give as direct output the most popular, trending topics. Typical topic detection methods that were identified during the literature review are being grouped in two categories; the application of probabilistic topic model algorithms and the application of feature-

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

based methods through clustering. Indicative examples in both categories are being given along the following lines:

- Application of Probabilistic Topic Model Algorithms: It concerns algorithms that aim to locate the hidden thematic structure in a large number of files. Most common approaches found in the literature include:
 - LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation): is a generative model that allows sets of observations to be explained by unobserved groups that explain why some parts of the data are similar⁶.
 - MF-LDA (Microblog Features LDA): It constitutes a variation of the classic LDA topic model that incorporates a clustering technique based on 5 post characteristics. The variation makes it easy to locate a topic in small texts (i.e. social networks & microblogs). (Yongtao Ye, Yajun Du, & Xia Fu, 2016)
 - HGTM (Hashtag Graph Topic Model): A similar LDA model that uses hashtags to better adapt to small texts (microblogs) and the modern way of writing posts. (Wang et al., 2014)
 - PLDA (Partially Labeled Dirichlet Allocation): Variation of the LDA model with partial pre-labelling of posts. (Chu, Wong, Chen, & Chi, 2014)
 - PAM (Pachinko Allocation Model): An alternative topic model that uses Directed Acyclic Graph-DAG to identify correlations between topics, extending the meaning of the topic as word and subtopics distribution. (L. Wei & McCallum, 2006)
- Application of feature-based methods/Clustering: Feature-based models focus on features of microblogs (eg hashtags, time, etc) and cluster these features rather than directly the posts themselves. Indicative examples of such clustering based on features are:
 - Keyword clustering
 - Clustering based on co-occurrences
 - Clustering by distribution
 - Feature/attribute based clustering
 - Online clustering Gaussian
 - Document-based clustering
 - Geographical clustering
 - Clustering based on semantic distance

4) Trend Detection: Three different flows can be recognised concerning trend detection step in comparison with the previous one, topic detection. In particular, trend detection can run by itself without the preceding topic detection step, it can run in parallel with topic detection or it can run separately and sequentially following the topic detection step. Each of these three different cases call for differentiated approaches, as described along the following lines.

- Cases where there is no topic detection step: Indicative processes identified in the academic literature for the case where only trend detection is being applied, without a prior topic detection, are Hawkes process or another stochastic model, the use of ontologies and frequency measurement, K-NN algorithms, etc.
- Cases where topic and trend detection run in parallel: Methods identified in this category include:

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Latent_Dirichlet_allocation

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- Dynamic Bayesian Network (DBN): This is a Trending Keywords algorithm. Then clustering on topics follows with the help of the DBSCAN algorithm.
- TF-IDF (term frequency-inverse document frequency): Statistical method that determines how important a word is in a file or set of files. Trending terms are identified and then grouping follows.
- Other popular search algorithms: e.g. QueueBurst algorithm for trending keywords detection, followed by grouping.
- Cases where topic detection precedes and trend detection follows: Methods identified in this category include:
 - Manual tracking: The user decides whether the topics identified are important or not.
 - Stochastic model that predicts the future trend of each topic.
 - Statistical analysis / parameter calculation and threshold control.
 - Statistical monitoring of a topic over time (compared to previous time periods).

5) Sentiment Analysis: This is not a common step in trend detection approaches, but it is considered of great added value in the context of ToyLabs. Therefore, it is seen separately as an additional step and approaches in the bibliography that use sentiment analysis for trend detection (and feedback management) are being explored.

One important issue regarding sentiment analysis is how sentiment will be measured. There is multitude of different approaches dealing with this issue, whereas direct correlation with the concept of **emotion** can be identified. In that view, the effort to interpret textual reports as sentiment cues is generally directly linked with the theory and research on emotions and its inherent subjective nature and restrictions are better perceived through this prism. Although the emotions research field is a complicated one, since it is related with multiple and diverse aspects, such as evolutionary, psychophysiological, neurological and other (Plutchik, 1980), there are also many relevant research studies that narrow down the field to be applied in real environments and therefore these studies are less focused on emotion modelling and more application-oriented, in that they adopt a simplistic view of emotions, i.e. limit their scope into polarity (pleasantness) categorisation, which is the task most commonly implied when referring to sentiment analysis and opinion mining. Computation of arousal (strength) estimation is also included in some cases, with sentiment often being represented in a Likert scale, e.g.: Very Negative, Negative, Neutral, Positive, Very Positive. However, there are approaches that maintain the link to the world of emotions, although very narrowed. As an example (Wu & Liang, 2011) and (Busso et al., 2004) use the following four categories in emotion recognition (in applications that use speech, facial expressions and other multimodal information): Anger, Sadness, Happiness, Neutral.

As far as classification of sentiment analysis approaches is concerned, many different research efforts can be found. One of the prevailing ones though groups sentiment analysis approaches into four main categories:

- **Keyword spotting:** This is the simplest and naivest approach, according to which text is classified based on the presence of fairly unambiguous affect words, e.g. happy, sad, afraid, bored. Simple phrase-level, or even word-level, sentiment analysis is being applied and therefore they are very cheap in terms of computational and time needs, but also not really reliable.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- **Lexical affinity:** Rather than simply detecting obvious polarity words like in keyword spotting, in these methods arbitrary words are assigned a probabilistic affinity for a particular emotion/sentiment polarity. In order to calculate these probabilities, some linguistic corpora are required. For example, “accident” might be assigned a 75 percent probability of indicating a negative sentiment, as in “car accident” or “hurt by accident.”
- **Statistical methods:** Machine learning algorithms are part of this category and they are deployed in sentiment analysis. A large training dataset of affectively annotated texts may be used to train a system to learn the affective value of words, taking into account the affective value of other arbitrary keywords, punctuation, and word co-occurrence frequencies. Statistical methods can co-exist with aspect-based techniques, further enhancing them.
- **Concept-level Approaches:** Concept-level approaches go beyond the simplistic polarity classification of text, to more informative results that capture the target of a sentiment as well as its nature. In order to do that, elements from knowledge representation are leveraged and semantically aware solutions are studied.

In order to better cite the reviewed approaches, a “social feedback and trends analysis” reporting schema is developed and applied. A set of appropriate criteria/features relevant to trends detection aspects are identified and described below:

- Publication
 - Paper title: (*self-explanatory*)
 - Year: (*self-explanatory*)
- Characteristics
 - Availability as a tool: indicating whether the approach/ methodology/ application under review is developing a tangible tool. The possible values are Yes/ No.
 - Sources: aiming at documenting the web/social media source or sources analysed by the paper under study in order to detect trends, topics and extract insights from users’ feedback.
 - Scientific/Application area: utilised to indicate the scientific and application areas of the reported approach, providing a general “label” that may give a high-level view of the area the paper under study is dealing with. More than one value can be attributed to this facet from a broad spectrum of possible values, including “Important events detection”, “emerging topics detection”, “popular topics identification” etc.
 - Real-time processing: reporting whether real-time data streams or historical data are being considered for the analysis that follows. The possible values are Yes/No/Not Specified.
- Experimentation
 - Dataset: If there is a specific dataset that was used for the experimentation, it should be inserted in this field.
 - Output: aiming at reporting what has been achieved through the experimentation

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- **Process steps:** In accordance with the aforementioned categorisation, five aggregated steps have been considered as relevant with trend detection and users' feedback analysis. These steps, though often encountered in most of the scientific approaches, are not obligatory. In that sense, this facet is divided into five sub-facets, one for each identified process step, where a "Yes" or "No" answer is required to document whether this step is part of the process described by the proposed approach of the paper under consideration. These steps/sub-facets are: Data collection step, Data processing step, Topic detection step, Trend detection step and Sentiment analysis step.
- **Algorithms/Technologies used:** Again this facet is divided into five sub-facet, one for each process step, in order to report the way each step is being accomplished in the context of the proposed by the paper approach/methodology. Any algorithms that are being used as part of the process described should be documented on the respective facet. The "Data processing step" is divided into two additional sub-facets. "Linguistic processing" is in many cases part of data processing actions and in that view a dedicated column has been considered to report what linguistic processing is being done. In the "Other Processing" column, any other, than linguistic, data processing actions can be presented there.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

Table 2-3 Literature Review for Social Feedback and Trends Analysis

Publication			Characteristics				Experimentation	
No	Paper title	Year	Availability as a tool	Sources	Scientific/Application area	Real-time processing	Dataset	Output
1	Detecting trends on the Web: A multidisciplinary approach (Dueñas-Fernández, Velásquez, & L'Huillier, 2014)	2014	No	Blogs, Twitter	Important events	No	A total of 200,890 objective texts and 268,800 tweets.	Among the 117 topics, 65 important events were manually detected.
2	Early detection method for emerging topics based on dynamic Bayesian networks in micro-blogging networks (Dang et al., 2016)	2016	No	Social media (not specified)	Emerging topics	Yes	A dataset from the Sina social network consisting of 13,973,119 tweets of 69,394 users.	54 emerging and 50 non-emerging topics were identified.
3	Trend detection in social networks using Hawkes processes (Pinto, Chahed, & Altman, 2015)	2015	No	Social media (not specified)	Emerging topics	Yes	2 datasets: The 1st has been exported from a social network. The 2nd from the most active websites for the period 03 / 2011-02 / 2012. This data was obtained from a university website.	The indicators of the methodology for 10 preselected topics are calculated and the corresponding summaries (cumulative sum of jumps, maximum of CIR process) are given.
4	Twittermonitor: trend detection over the twitter	2010	Yes	Twitter	Popular topics	Yes	A sample of posts on Twitter (around 10 million per day)	The output is presented on the tool's web

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

	stream (Mathioudakis & Koudas, 2010b)							application trends are detected in real time.
5	Monitoring trends on Facebook (Pletikosa, Irena; Michahelles, 2011)	2011	No	Facebook	Popular identification topics	Yes	2,000,000 public posts, over a 4-day period, where 3 major events were expected to be detected. 10 experiments with 1000 posts each were performed.	Two of the three events were successfully detected, while the third due to the diversity of the terms referring to it was incompletely detected.
6	Social networking trends and dynamics detection via a cloud-based framework design (Cloud4Trends) (Vakali, Giatsoglou, & Antaris, 2012)	2012	Yes	Blogs, Twitter	Popular identification topics	Yes	Data collected from the Twitter Streaming API & from the Google Blogger API in real time, through parsers.	The output is presented on the tool's web application trends are detected in real time.
7	Hot Topic Extraction Based on Chinese Microblog's Features Topic Model (Yongtao Ye et al., 2016)	2016	No	Social media (not specified)	Popular identification topics	Yes	Data from the social network of Sina. The dataset contains 200,000 posts, 2/3 of which are used as learning data.	The output is popular topics, and CR index is defined to check efficiency
8	Event detection and popularity prediction in microblogs (Zhang et al., 2015)	2015	No	Microblogs	Important detection events	Yes	2 datasets:. The 1st consists of 31 million posts on Twitter with a random sample of 313,000 users. The 2nd is the Chinese Sina. Users sare selected based on the popular topics	As the results of the experiment are given the sets of grouped popular words (topics) and the prediction of their impact.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

							suggested by the medium (119,000 users).	
9	Deriving market intelligence from microblogs (Li & Li, 2013)	2013	No	Microblogs	Popular identification topics	Yes	2 experiments with data collected from Twitter using querying on its API. Searches are being used about three companies and three products.	The output includes the popular topics, the emotional orientation of the posts & conclusions
10	Hashtag Graph based Topic Model for Tweet Mining (Wang et al., 2014)	2014	No	Twitter	Topic detection	Not specified	The existing dataset "TweetData", containing 16 million posts from Twitter sampled between 23/01/2011 and 8/02/2011.	The topics & their representative hashtags that the model discovers (60 topics are detected)
11	PoliTwi: Early detection of emerging political topics on twitter and the impact on concept-level sentiment analysis (Rill, Reinel, Scheidt, & Zicari, 2014)	2014	Yes	Twitter	Emerging topics detection (politics)	Yes	Data is collected from the Twitter Streaming API and stored in a PostgreSQL database before pre-processing.	Presentation of top popular topics along with sentiment analysis on different channels (Twitter, website and mobile application).
12	A prerecognition model for hot topic discovery based on microblogging data (Zhu & Yu, 2014)	2014	No	Microblogs	Popular identification topics	Yes	A total of 2,000,000 posts from the social network Sina. After the pre-processing stage, there are 675,439 posts in 2014/01/01 to 2014/04/30. Some data is used as a training dataset by 2014/01/01	Sorted list of the most popular topics (& sub-topics) that have been detected, along with some statistics and indicators

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

							to 2014/01/31 and balances for review.	
13	Discovering hot topics using Twitter streaming data social topic detection and geographic clustering (Kim, Lee, & Kyeong, 2013)	2013	No	Social media (not specified)	Topic detection (per location)	Yes	18,720,902 geo-tagged Twitter posts in US (23/3 /2013-1/ 4/2013)	9 emerging topics were identified in a semi-automatic manner and graphical representations for each one of them were created. Geographic clustering was used to specify the results by state and region.
14	Sociopedia: An Interactive System for Event Detection and Trend Analysis for Twitter Data (Kaushik, Apoorva Chandra, Mallya, Chaitanya, & Kamath, 2016)	2016	Yes	Twitter	Trend detection	No	Experimental testing for 4 datasets on 4 different predefined topics, with about 40000 Twitter posts each.	Results through an online platform based on user's search
15	Predicting the topic influence trends in social media with multiple models (Han et al., 2014)	2014	No	Social media (not specified)	Trend detection	No	18,012,123 users are collected, their relationships and Twitter posts for a period of one month. For the geographic control, a 2nd dataset is used by the Chinese network Sina.	For topics selected by the users, forecast is given for their future influence in the form of time series.
16	BlogPulse: Automated Trend Discovery for Weblogs (Glance, Glance, Hurst, & Tomokiyo, 2004)	2004	Yes	Blogs	Popular identification topics	No	Not specified	Topics and their inclination/trend in time, with the help of automated algorithms.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

17	Microblog Topic Detection Based on LDA Model and Single-Pass Clustering (Huang, Yang, Mahmood, & Wang, 2012)	2012	No	Microblogs	Topic detection	Yes	Checking the methodology in a set of 108,122 posts from Sina-microblog in August 2011 with the help of a Web crawler.	Topics known in advance in order to test the efficiency of the method in their detection, as compared to the SVM model.
18	TwitterStand: News in Tweets (Sankaranarayanan, Samet, Teitler, Lieberman, & Sperling, 2009)	2009	Yes	Twitter	Event detection	No	Collection of posts from 4 different feeds. Indicative: a service configured to search for posts with specific words, an algorithm (BirdDog) selecting users etc.	Results as groups of topics along with their geographical mapping
19	Open Domain Event Extraction from Twitter (TwiCal) (Ritter, Mausam, Etzioni, & Clark, 2012)	2012	Yes	Twitter	Event detection	No	100 million Twitter posts in November 2011 (Twitter Streaming API), using a set of time keywords such as "today", "tomorrow", names of days, months etc.	The most important events for each broader category in the form of entities, i.e. the most typical phrases for each. The top 5 findings are presented
20	An unsupervised framework of exploring events on twitter: filtering, extraction and categorization (Zhou, Chen, & He, 2015)	2015	No	Twitter	Event detection	No	2 datasets from Twitter. The 1st has been manually collected (December 2010), the 2nd contains 60 million unlabelled posts.	The most important topics, typical keywords for each and a categorisation of topics according to the broader field they belong to.
21	Real-time event detection for online behavioral analysis of big social data (Nguyen & Jung, 2017)	2017	No	Social media (not specified)	Event detection	Yes	2 existing datasets from Twitter from a previous study, "FA	Each event is represented by a set of keywords and the results are evaluated

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

									Cup" and "Super Tuesday"	"Super	based on three features: Topic Recall (TOP-REC), Keyword Precision (K-PREC) and Keyword ReCall (K-REC) for each subject.
22	Microblog Contagiousness Measurement and Emerging Outbreak Monitoring (Chu et al., 2014)	Topic and	2014	No	Twitter	Emerging detection	topics	No	2 datasets from Twitter: the 1st with 130 million posts, of which 3.3% with hashtags (11 / 2008-05/2009) and the 2nd with 79 million posts, of which 11% with hashtags (01 / 2010-11 / 2010)		The popular topics represented by their main hashtag, and their propagation parameter

Publication			Steps					Algorithms/Technologies Used						
No	Paper title	Year	Data collection step	Data processing step	Topic detection step	Trend detection step	Sentiment analysis step	Data collection step	Data processing step		Topic detection step		Trend detection step	Sentiment analysis step
									Linguistic Processing	Other Processing	Topic model & other algorithms	Grouping/Clustering		
1	Detecting trends on the Web: A multidisciplinary approach	2014	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Crawler at the selected sources	Removing stop-words, html items & external	-	LDA	-	Manually	SentiWord Net platform

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

								links, stemming						
2	Early detection method for emerging topics based on dynamic bayesian networks in micro-blogging networks	2016	Yes	No	Yes		No	Directly through Sina API	-	-	K-Means	DBSCAN, keyword clustering	DBN, trending keywords	-
3	Trend detection in social networks using Hawkes processes	2015	No	No	No	Yes	No	-	-	-	Manually	Hawkes process, stochastic model	-	
4	Twittermonitor: trend detection over the twitter stream	2010	Yes	No	Yes		No	Directly through Twitter API	-	-	-	GroupBurst algorithm, keyword clustering, clustering based on co-occurrences	QueueBurst algorithm, trending keywords	-
5	Monitoring trends on Facebook	2011	Yes	Yes	Yes		No	Simple algorithm retrieving public posts from Facebook every 10'	Removing stop-words & external links	-	-	Clustering based on concurrent appearance, clustering by distribution	TF-IDF, trending terms	-

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

6	Social networking trends and dynamics detection via a cloud-based framework design (Cloud4Trends)	2012	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Twitter and Blog parsers	Removing stop-words, text refinement, stemming	Presentation of data from different sources with a common model	-	Feature/attribute based clustering, online clustering Gaussian, document-based clustering	TF-IDF, trending topics	-
7	Hot Topic Extraction Based on Chinese Microblog's Features Topic Model	2016	No	Yes	Yes		No	-	Removing stop-words & punctuation	Grouping of posts by date	MF-LDA	Grouping based on attributes	Trending posts	-
8	Event detection and popularity prediction in microblogs	2015	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	-	Removing stop-words, excluding posts with fewer than 3 words	Word weighting	Viterbi Algorithm	Clustering based on concurrent appearance, clustering by distribution	Emerging keywords, LDA model for predicting interest of users in the future, linear propagation model for each topic	-
9	Deriving market intelligence from microblogs	2013	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Crawler at the selected sources	Tagging (POS) in words		-		TF-IDF, trending topics	WordNet platform, SVM model

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

10	Hashtag Graph based Topic Model for Tweet Mining	2014	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	-	Basic Normalization Steps	Removal of retweets & tweets without hashtags	HGTM (Hashtag graph topic model), LDA-like	Clustering based on hashtags	-	-
11	PoliTwi: Early detection of emerging political topics on twitter and the impact on concept-level sentiment analysis	2014	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Crawler at the selected sources	-	Removal of hashtags, sentiment hashtags & emoticons	-	Clustering based on hashtags	Comparison of the frequency of a topic (number of posts) in the current period than the previous one	Use of sentiment hashtags in comparison with the previous period
12	A prerecognition model for hot topic discovery based on microblogging data	2014	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Crawler at the selected sources (microblog APIs)	Removing stop-words, removing unwanted words	Removal of hashtags and direct mapping of them in topics	LDA, PAM, k-NN algorithm	Grouping keywords, grouping topics	Statistical parameter computation, threshold control	-
13	Discovering hot topics using Twitter streaming data social topic detection and geographic clustering	2013	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Directly through Twitter API	-	Limiting geographically marked data for a specific range	-	Manual grouping (keyword overview)	Trending keywords, word frequency, grouping by region	-
14	Sociopedia: An Interactive System for Event Detection	2015	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	With the help of the tool	Removing stop-words,	Time sorting and counting of	CMU tweet parser,	-	Ontologies and	-

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

	and Trend Analysis for Twitter Data							Sysomos, displaying the time stamp, the location, the sentiment and the identity of the user.	blocking foreign language words & removing posts with many symbols.	posts on a daily basis	POS tagger		mention frequency	
15	Predicting the topic influence trends in social media with multiple models	2014	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	-	Removing stop-words, stemming	-	-	-	k-NN algorithm	-
16	BlogPulse: Automated Trend for Discovery Weblogs	2004	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Web Spider at the selected sources (Intelligence Spider)	Blocking foreign language posts, segmentation of text, conversion of individual elements into lower case.	Segmentation of HTML nodes	-	Key/phrase level grouping, similarity grouping.	Monitoring of the frequency of occurrence of a subject/topic in time	-
17	Microblog Topic Detection Based on LDA	2012	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Web crawler algorithm at the	Text segmentation on system CTCLAS	-	LDA	Grouping based on LDA	-	-

	Model and Single-Pass Clustering							selected sources						
18	TwitterStand: News in Tweets	2009	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Collection of posts from different sources and filtering through a classifier to be labelled as new or not.	Natural Language Processing-NLP, Part-Of-Speech-POS tagging, Named-Entity Recognition-NER	-	Gaussian, TF-IDF	Geographical clustering, post-level clustering	TF-IDF, trending topics	-
19	Open Domain Extraction from Twitter (TwiCal)	2012	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Directly through Twitter API	POS tagging, semantic identification of entities	-	Thread/topic detection with POS tagger and a trained dataset	LinkLDA, Bayesian model for grouping events under wider categories	Probabilistic event significance calculation according to the number of posts and the timestamp	-
20	An unsupervised framework of exploring events on twitter: filtering, extraction and categorization	2015	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Directly through Twitter API	Stemming, POS tagging, semantic identification of entities	Filtering posts depending on whether they contain words	-	LECM model, Bayesian model	-	-

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

										within a particular set, feature-based filtering, SVM model				
21	Real-time event detection for online behavioral analysis of big social data	2017	Yes	Yes	Yes		No	Directly through Twitter API using search filtering	Text editing, removal of symbols, links, labels, hashtags reduction in keywords, removal of unnecessary words	Importing data in a normalised form	-	Segmentation based on semantic distance (graph), OPTICS algorithm	Emerging terms	-
22	Microblog Topic Contagiousness Measurement and Emerging Outbreak Monitoring	2014	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	-	-	Removal of posts without hashtags	PLDA, Stanford Topic Modeling Toolbox	-	Calculation of propagation parameter R using Bayesian-inference Python package, SIR model	-

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.3.3 Key take-aways

The extensive desk research that took place in the field of web based trends detection and analysis revealed certain useful insights that highlight both the research potential of the field on which ToyLabs may contribute, as well as the opportunities that arise for the toy industry sector if an appropriate approach for web and social media trends detection is to be applied.

During the academic literature analysis of this field, it became apparent that there is no plethora of approaches/papers dealing with the application of social network analysis for trends detection and feedback management, especially on what concerns the manufacturing sector, whereas at the same time the association of this research field (i.e. trends detection) with the market and the market trends is still blurry, leaving open space for further research and development in the context of ToyLabs. Furthermore, it can be noticed that there cannot be found a lot of attempts developing a generic, univocal framework that goes beyond a singular application domain; a fact that can be attributed to the broad definition of what a trend is (Dueñas-Fernández et al., 2014). Despite this fact, in the context of the present deliverable, a focused attempt was made to find certain common grounds among these differentiated approaches. This attempt ended up with the identification of the five steps presented in the previous section that are classifying the processes encountered in trend detection projects, in an almost sequential flow. In a deeper analysis, it can be stressed that although the first four steps are part of almost every approach studied, presenting only variations on the ways that these approaches are being implemented, the last step, sentiment analysis, was hardly met, revealing that it is not yet considered an established approach when dealing with web/social media trends. Finally, it can be observed that in most cases a completely automatic methodology is not possible and intervention of users/experts is imposed to manually process certain actions.

2.4 AUGMENTED REALITY FOR FEEDBACK GATHERING

2.4.1 Background

Today, we live in a highly competitive and dynamic business environment, the manufacturing industry is facing new challenges, which require a holistic perspective on the four main classes of manufacturing attributes, i.e., cost, time, quality, and flexibility⁷ of manufacturing companies (and toy manufacturers amongst them) should be producing innovative products at low cost and reduced time-to-market. High product-mix with low volume, customisation to meet the individual demands of the customers, increasing legislation of environmental and other issues have further made

⁷ Chrysolouris G (2006) Manufacturing Systems – Theory and Practice, 2nd ed. Springer-Verlag, New York.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

manufacturing processes more complex and demanding⁸. The evaluation of a product involves a demonstration of the designer's work and the visualisation should demonstrate that the design fits spatially and aesthetically into its environment⁹. This process of product design evaluation is important to get feedback from the user's perception in different fields such as functional, aesthetical or usability and to make sure that the product characteristics meet the user needs. In this context, Augmented Reality can be used as a powerful tool in the hands of designers to acquire the early feedback they need to come up with truly novel design that respond to the expectations of the manufacturer. The application of Augmented Reality can reduce cost and time and also improve the quality of product evaluations integrating the context elements and a more natural interaction with virtual elements¹⁰.

According to Wikipedia¹¹, Augmented Reality is a novel technology allows to have a live (real-time) view of a physical environment with some of its objects being augmented with the use of computer generated sensory input, such as audio, video, or images. In contrast to Virtual Reality (VR) where the whole "world" the user interacts with is virtual (e.g. computer generated), Augmented Reality offers to user a real-world experience, as the majority of the scenery he is witnessing is the real environment in front of him.

The main techniques used for Augmented Reality deal with the blending, in real-time, of different objects with the real environment, by projecting overlaying information or graphics on specific pre-defined surfaces (often pre-calculated) that act as the placeholders for such information.

Although a not so young technology and with having already a large base of applications in domains as military, medicine and manufacturing^{12,13}, Augmented Reality is becoming mainstream in the last couple of years, as the advantages in computing, and more specifically in mobile computing allowed the technology to be introduced in handheld devices.

In fact, the history of Augmented Reality can be tracked back to 1990, however, it successfully drew the attention of the public until recent years when some big firms like Google and Facebook invested huge capital in developing Augmented Reality¹⁴. Over the past years, a large number of devices that supported it has been developed, such as Head Up Displays (HUDs), however the computing power of today's mobile phones alongside with their integrated sensors (e.g. cameras, microphones,

⁸ Nee, A.Y.C.; Ong, S.K.; Chryssolouris, G.; Mourtzis, D. (2012) [Augmented Reality applications in design and manufacturing](#) CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology vol. 61 (2) p. 657-679

⁹ Ahlers KH, Kramer A, Breen DE, Chevalier P-Y, Tuceryan M, Whitaker RT. Distributed Augmented Reality for collaborative design applications. Computer Graphics Forum 1995; 14(3):3-14, Blackwell Science Ltd.

¹⁰ Ye J, Badiyani S, Raja V, Schlegel T. Applications of virtual reality in product design evaluation. In Human-Computer Interaction. HCI Applications and Services, 2007; pp. 1190-1199. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

¹¹ Augmented Reality: Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Augmented_reality

¹² Ong SK, Nee AYC (2004) Virtual and Augmented Reality Applications in Manufacturing, Springer, London. ISBN 1-85233-796-6

¹³ Yuan ML, Ong SK, Nee AYC (2008) Augmented Reality Applications in Manufacturing: a Survey. International Journal of Production Research 46(10):2702-2742

¹⁴ How the Toy Industry Innovates with Augmented Reality (2016). Available at: <http://www.globaltoynews.com/2016/01/how-the-toy-industry-innovates-with-augmented-reality.html>

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

accelerometers, etc.) made it possible to push this technology to ordinary users. Nowadays, Augmented Reality can be offered to people through eyeglasses and smart phones, with the latter being the cheapest and most widespread option, and in this context Augmented Reality is now starting to get introduced to other sectors, with retail being one of the most promising one, both in terms of generating novel user experiences, as well as in terms of utilisation by end-users.

In just over a decade, Augmented Reality technology has matured and proven to be an innovative and effective solution to help solve some of the critical problems to simulate, assist and improve manufacturing processes before they are to be carried out. This would ensure that activities, such as design, planning, machining, etc., are done right-the-first-time without the need for subsequent re-work and modifications.

TOYLABS will design and build an Augmented Reality component for getting users' feedback on new concepts through a virtual experience of playing with toys which are still at the design phase. Through Augmented Reality, the user focus groups will be able to gain a complete understanding of the look and feel of the toys, as well as of their operation/ gameplay and on the basis of their experience and preferences to provide recommendations either for improving or for customising the concept.

2.4.2 Landscape Review

Literature Review

During the last years, there has been interesting research work on implementing Augmented Reality in activities related to product design and development, including the collection of feedback and in general the assessment of a new product even from the design or the prototyping phase, so much before a fully featured version of the final product becomes available. Indicative related applications that augmented reality has or is being applied include early visualization of products, simulation of usage, ergonomic analysis, hybrid prototyping and quality assurance.

Starting from the product design phase, reviewing alternative designs – in terms of getting feedback and hints for improvement – is a useful, however difficult process when involving people (like end-users or domain experts) who are not experienced in reviewing industrial designs. For this reason, feedback is being provided by using one or more prototypes of final product. These prototypes can be real or virtual. Unfortunately, physical prototypes show some limitations; for example, they do not allow variants of shape and material, nor support interactive behaviour (Re, 2013). In the literature, Augmented Reality is being thoroughly examined and used in order to support this part of the process (Friedrich & Friedrich, 2002; Fründ, Gausemeier, Matysczok, & Radkowski, 2005). The bulk of the studies that have been identified focus on the in usage of AR either for augmented design or for augmented prototyping. In both cases AR technology has been exploited to evaluate product design by representing virtual information and/or the virtual object directly into the real

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

environment. Next, selected works utilising Augmented Reality for getting feedback and evaluating product designs and/or prototypes, as found during our literature review, are presented:

Fata Morgana project (Klinker et al., 2002) proposed AR for the visualization of a virtual car in a show room. For this reason, an immersive visualization system has been used and the behaviour of designer during aesthetic evaluation of a car has been analysed.

Sidharta, Oliver and Sannier (2006) proposed using Augmented Reality for a collaborative environment for the evaluation of mechanical products. In this work, the design review is performed by means of a HMDs with users located remotely.

In a most recent work, Augmented Reality has been used for evaluating the functional behaviour of electronic products (Park, Moon, & Lee, 2009). The user, by means of a sort of stylus, could interact with the virtual representation of the object, which simulates the behaviour of the real product through a state machine. A user study conducted with testers showed better interaction performances with immersive stereo AR than the screen based one.

A very interesting application of Augmented Reality has been developed by Botta Design, that created an app helping users to try on different watch designs to show exactly how the watch would look like if the users were wearing it (Shumaker & Lackey, 2015).

While the aforementioned works mostly focus on using Augmented Reality for getting feedback and reviewing the design of a new product, there is also a series of cases in the literature referring to getting feedback in the prototyping phase. While physical prototypes are being developed easily thanks to additive manufacturing, for complex products the prototypes cannot provide an accurate representation of all the product details like mechanical construction, material, assembly, electronic systems etc. In such cases AR has been considered a valuable tool for bridging the gap between the prototype and the actual product (Topal, 2015). Incorporating Augmented Reality with prototypes (either virtual or physical) is met in the literature as augmented prototyping, which may have six categories/ dimensions depending on the utilization of AR and the scope of using it: geometric modelling, interactive painting, layout design, information appliances, automotive design and augmented engineering (Verlinden, De Smit, Peeters, & Van Gelderen, 2003).

Different experimental tools for augmented prototyping have been developed over the years. Indicatively the following can be selected:

- The AR tool SKIN which works by projecting materials, textures and colours as flat images onto surfaces of 3D mock ups (Saakes & Van der Lugt, 2007).
- The work of Park, Moon and Lee (2009) who have proposed a system that consists of a pointer and an object for prototyping handheld products.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- ARMO, short for Augmented Reality based reconfigurable Mock up, combining rapid prototyping with AR based manipulation of shapes, colours, textures and user interfaces (Jin, Kim, & Park, 2007).
- The work of Balcisoy et al., who created an AR framework for testing product design and evaluating prototypes (Balcisoy & Kallmann, 2000).
- AF – Augmented Foam, a tangible AR framework created for helping designers make high-fidelity prototypes for design ideas in short times (Lee & Park, 2006)
- The most recent work of (Berning et al., 2013) using 360 degrees interactive video for AR prototyping.

Concluding, related literature and specific studies on the field indicate that the application of AR to product development is an interesting approach mostly due to the fact that blending physical prototypes with AR technologies do lead to an improved perception and better understanding of the examined prototype by the users asked to evaluate it.

Augmented Reality in the Toy Industry

Augmented Reality provides the toy industry with a revolution where it can both be used to simulate toys prior to their creation, in order to cover all users' requirements and preferences, while it is also being used to make toys more interactive, using simple devices that users possess such as smartphones or tablets¹⁵. When referring to the latter, users can enhance the physical world as they play and one can find a constantly growing list of toys and games that use Augmented Reality principles to become more interactive. Huge companies are starting to capitalise on this trend; for example, Disney has announced Disney Dream Play¹⁶ where known Disney characters come to life using stationary Augmented Reality tags and a tablet and mobile device app, while Sony's Wonderbook¹⁷ is the gaming giant's first standalone foray into Augmented Reality, and it is sold as an add-on to the popular PlayStation 3 and motion sensing controller, PlayStation Move. Other examples include Lego Fusion, Lego X¹⁸, Dr. King Zoo Augmented Reality¹⁹, Toy Car RC²⁰, or the very popular game Pokémon Go²¹. However, according to Hung²², there are many research challenges with respect to Augmented Reality toys that have yet to be overcome before the Augmented Reality toy market is more prevalent, as "... *the development process of Augmented Reality*

¹⁵ Gottlieb, R (2016). How the Toy Industry Innovates with Augmented Reality. Available at: <http://www.globaltoynews.com/2016/01/how-the-toy-industry-innovates-with-augmented-reality.html>

¹⁶ McWherton, M. (2013). DreamPlay app a new leap in AR, not part of Disney Infinity project, say creators. Available at: <https://www.polygon.com/2013/1/9/3851974/disney-dreamplay-ar-app-disney-infinity>

¹⁷ Sony Wonderbook. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wonderbook>

¹⁸ Howarth, D. (2015). Lego X turns toy building blocks into a digital modelling kit for designers. <https://www.dezeen.com/2015/01/28/lego-x-gravity-digital-modelling-kit/>

¹⁹ Dr. King Zoo App. <https://www.joyaether.com/portfolio/dr-king-zoo-ar-app/>

²⁰ Toy Car RC Augmented Reality. Available at: <http://toywheel.com/game/toy-car-rc/>

²¹ Pokémon Go. <http://www.pokemongo.com>

²² Hung, P. Will Augmented Reality be the Next Big Thing for Toys? Augmented Reality (Augmented Reality) Toys Computing Management. Available at: <https://cie.acm.org/articles/will-augmented-reality-be-next-big-thing-toys/>

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

toys may be costly, lengthy, and difficult due to technological challenges, while ... another exacerbating issue is a mobile service with technological standards for Augmented Reality toys has yet to be established within the global toy industry.”

On the other side of using Augmented Reality for simulating a toy during its design phase, not much has been done. The toy “Lego Model Demonstrator” mentioned above is an example of using Augmented Reality to visualise a model and uses the concept of design augmentation and visualisation, but from the perspective of the end user. The introduction of this technology into the TOYLABS platform is completely targeting this exact stage, that of model visualisation during the initial design and manufacturing phases in order to not only showcase a future product, but most importantly to gather feedback from different stakeholders, towards strengthening the market acceptance and in this manner the commercial success of a product. In order to do this, TOYLABS has devised a methodology (described at a high level below) that suggest a circular way of working for setting up the platform with ready-to-visualise Augmented Reality models, which are tightly linked with simple feedback gathering tools. In parallel to this, and based on the overall user and system requirements, as well as the methodology’s demands, TOYLABS will choose the most convenient IT infrastructure to provide these Augmented Reality services to as many users as possible.

Augmented Reality Platforms Comparison

The section below provides a list of the most popular Augmented Reality platforms which are being considered for inclusion in the TOYLABS ecosystem. It needs to be noted that the comparison performed below provides an overview of available solutions, and the criteria for the selection of the prevailing platform will be devised in WP3, alongside with the user stories of the platform, the technical requirements, and the demonstrator requirements as well.

In general, the Augmented Reality method for feedback gathering to be used in TOYLABS will take into consideration certain aspects that will derive from the overall TOYLABS methodology, such as need for low cost operation, easy to use UI, availability (mostly) over handheld devices, interactive features for feedback retrieval, etc. These aspects will be evaluated during M7 and M8 of the project, prior to the implementation of the first prototype Augmented Reality component of the project, following the final design of the system architecture.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

Table 2-4. Comparison of Augmented Reality Platforms

Name	Owner	Open Source	License	Models Supported (2D/3D)	Recognition (of fixed/moving objects)	Geolocation	Web Support	Handheld Devices	Platforms Support
3DAR	Spot Metrix, Inc.	Yes	Free, Commercial SDK	2D	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	• iOS
ALVAR	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland.	Yes	Free	2D/3D	Yes	No	Yes	No	• Android, iOS, Windows, Flash
BazAR	Computer Vision Laboratory - CVLAB	Yes	GPL	2D	Yes	No	Yes	No	• Linux, OSX, Windows
AndAR	ARToolworks	Yes	LPGL v3	2d/3d	Yes	No	Yes	No	• Android
ARToolKit	DAQRI	Yes	LPGL v3	2D / 3D through 3rd party library	Yes	Yes	Yes, with jsAugmented RealityToolkit (JavaScript)	Yes	• iOS • Android • Mac OS • Linux • Windows
ArUco	ArUco	Yes	BSD	2D	Yes	N/A	Yes	No	• BSD • Linux • Windows

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

Augmented Reality-media	Inglobe Technologies	No	Commercial	2D/ 3D	Yes	N/A	Yes, with Unity Plugin	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iOS • Android
Aurasma	HP	Yes	Free, Commercial SDK	2d/3d	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iOS • Android
BeyondAR	BeyondAR	Yes	Apache 2.0	2D/ 3D	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Android
CatChoom	Catchoom	No	Commercial	2D / 3D	Yes	N/A	Yes (with Plugin)	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iOS • Android
DroidAR	Bitstars	Yes	GPLv3 and Commercial	2D / 3D	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Android • iOS
EasyAR	Vision Star Technologies	No	Commercial	2D / 3D	Yes (with paid PRO version)	Yes	Yes	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iOS • Android • Windows • Mac OS • UWP, • Unity Editor
FIWARE Augmented Reality Generic Enabler	DFKI	Yes - except Xml3D.js	GPL v.3	3D through Add-on Generic Enabler	Yes	Yes, Through Add-on Generic Enabler	HTML5 Capable (with Javascript)	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All that support HTML5
Goblin XNA	Columbia University	Yes	BSD	2D/3D	Yes	No	Yes	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

iOS Augmented Reality Engine	Apple	No	N/A	3D	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	• iOS
Kudan	Kudan Ltd	No	Commercial	3D	Yes	No	Yes, with Unity Plugin	Yes	• iOS • Android
Layar	Blipparr Group	No	Commercial	2D / 3D	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	• Android • iOS
Maxst AR	Maxst	Yes	Free (watermarked) – Paid no Watermark	2D / 3D	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	• iOS • Android • Windows • Mac OSX
Metaio	Apple	NO	Commercial	2D / 3D	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	• iOS • Android • Windows • Mac OSX
mixare	Peer Srl	Yes	GPLv3	2D / 3D	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	• Android • iOS
MxrToolkit	Mixed Reality Lab Singapore	Open Source	Open	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	• N/A
NyarToolkit	Nayatla	Open Source, Commercial SDK	Open	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	• Android, Linux, Windows, Flash

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

Ostrich	TechNotec ture	Yes	Open	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linux, OSX, Windows
PanicAR	DoPanic	Yes	Free, Commerci al SDK	2D/3D	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Android • iOS
PointCloud Library	PointCloud s.org	Yes	BSD	Yes	Yes	N/A	Yes	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linux • MacOS • Windows • Android • iOS
PRAugmente dReality	DrupalCon	Yes	Open	2d/3d	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
RoboCortex Rox	Robocorte x	No	Commerci al	3D	Yes	N/A	N/A	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A
SLARToolkit	Developer media	Yes	open	2d/3d	Yes	N/A	N/A	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A
SSTT Bounce	Computer Graphics at Schmalkal den University of Applied Science	Closed source	open	2d	Yes	No	Yes	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Android, iOS, Windows Mobile, Linux, OSX, Windows
T-Immersion	Total Immersion	No	Commerci al	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows • Linux • MacOS • Android • iOS

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

									<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows Mobile
Vuforia	PTC Inc.	No	Commercial	3D through 3 rd party library	Yes	No	Yes, with Unity Plugin & Player	Yes, with Unity Plugin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All
Wikitude	Wikitude	No	Commercial	3D	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iOS • Android
WinAR	National University of Singapore	Yes	Free, Commercial SDK	2d/3d	Yes	N/A	N/A	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows
Xzing	Xzing	Yes	Commercial	2D	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Android • OS • Windows • WebG

As identified by the landscape review conducted by the consortium concerning Augmented Reality SDKs, it is evident that there are numerous solutions, which are both of open source as well as of commercial nature. Some of them are offered completely for free, however the majority of the solutions are offered on paid plans, which offer enhanced capabilities and features over their free plans.

Support for 3D objects is not present in all SDKs and it mainly has to do with the underlying algorithms and the targeted devices to be used, as 3D representations require higher processing power and more precise vectoring and mark-up patterns (to trigger the Augmented Reality models), which are things that are mostly provided by high-end devices.

It is also important to note that the majority of those SDKs are supporting handheld devices, as they are considered the most appropriate medium for Augmented Reality (putting aside devices such as Smart Glasses which are at experimental phases). Web based or even desktop-based Augmented Reality is also supported by them, however such solutions seem to be quite unpleasant

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

to use, and that is the reason one is witnessing a constant shift towards the support of modern mobile platforms such as Android and iOS.

2.4.3 Augmented Reality as part of the TOYLABS Integrated Methodology

As TOYLABS aims to offer a novel technology platform to the toy industry to rapidly and more effectively produce new products that highly satisfy their customers, Augmented Reality is regarded as an important technology asset that could complement the platform. TOYLABS is tasked to design and provide through Augmented Reality an intuitive human interface to make Augmented Reality a powerful tool in the hands of toy manufacturers. The activities that will take place along the project duration will make sure that the approach and application developed will lead to a flexible and light solution that will address the issue of availability for different users, facilitating remote collaboration of different stakeholders' groups and on different devices with varying degrees of immersion and mobility to support feedback gathering, picking up trends, and collecting issues, annotations and votes through user-participation.

In this context, Augmented Reality as part of the TOYLABS platform is envisaged to truly provide a novel experience to end-users and toy experts, allowing them to witness and interact with prototypes before they reach the production stage, and provide feedback back to manufactures.

Figure 2-4 Intervention of Augmented Reality (red points in the figure) in the TOYLABS High Level Workflow Process

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.4.4 Key take-aways

As identified in the previous sections, Augmented Reality is a novel technology for the Toy Industry and its potential is mostly witnessed during playtime (e.g. as part of a toy or of a game itself, especially in the areas of videogames). However, as the literature review revealed, alongside with trends and statistics of the industry, Augmented Reality holds a significant advantage that can be used by toy manufacturers in order to create virtual representation of early designs, prototypes as well as finalised (or semi-finalised) products, towards improving the market acceptance rates and their commercial success. Especially in the domain of toys, where other stakeholders are involved (such as safety experts or pedagogues), it is pivotal to accelerate time to market but at the same time conduct numerous checks and assessments of prototypes, and the virtualisation that can be offered by Augmented Reality is in a position to bring those requirements together, which is of course impossible in the case the assessment is performed with physical prototypes, due mainly to time delays. As such, the analysis performed showed that there is a brilliant potential to utilise Augmented Reality as a novel feedback mechanism.

Finally, from the point of Augmented Reality platforms and SDKs, there is a plethora of tools offered at this point, under various licensing and pricing schemes. Most of those target handheld devices, which are considered the most appropriate medium for Augmented Reality (together with Smart Glasses). However, there is not a clear winner or an SDK that is highly dominant at the moment, while a crucial factor to choose an SDK is highly linked with the type of devices that the audience can use, and whether these SDKs are natively supported in those devices.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.5 PARTNER MATCHING

2.5.1 Background

From more than 5.000 toy companies in Europe over 99% are SMEs, approximately 88% of these companies are micro enterprises with less than 10 employees.²³

In the current competitive market, most of these toy companies are conditioned by a set of structural weaknesses and environment threats that limit their ability to survive.

The bad business dynamics of recent years marked by the continuous movement of closing companies greater than that of news ones, as well as the negative evolution of the business balance of most of them, only increase the problem

The literature²⁴ proposes new business models that allow to boost the "exit" of the crisis. All models define subcontracting as the only means of adaptation. But the approach is totally different depending on the type of company.

Main goal and description of all business models are focused on partner matching as a success of outsourcing work.

Two different business models are described below, as well as the actions that a company must take to improve its situation in each one of the product development stages (pre-production, production and post-production).

2.5.1.1 *The "challenging", "global" or "proactive" company*

This company profile seeks cooperation with other companies to elude the limitations of small size (lack of financial, technical and human resources).

This company profile bets on more powerful brands and their own distribution networks, and even, the creation of sales subsidiaries. These own external commercial structures improve the image of the company's products and the degree of control, offer after-sales service and receive direct market information

²³ <https://www.toyindustries.eu/resource/smes-european-toy-sector/>

²⁴ Crisis, actitudes directivas y estrategia en los sectores manufactureros tradicionales
<http://www.redalyc.org/html/433/43301406/>

Barker, V. L. y Barr, P. (2002): "Linking top manager attributions to strategic reorientation in declining firms attempting turnarounds. Journal of Business Research, 55: 963-979k.

Barker, V. L. y Duhaime, I (1997): "Strategic Change in the turnaround process: theory and empirical evidence". Strategic Management Journal, 18: 13-38.

Barker, V. L. y Mone, M. (1998): "The mechanistic structure shift and strategic reorientation in declining firms attempting turnarounds". Human Relations, 51: 1227-1258.
de los 90, Ed. Civitas, Madrid, pp. 51-69.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Businesses in this profile must take advantage of "multilocation".

The multilocation does not suppose the dismantling of the industrial production but a change of mentality in the organization of the resources. Ignoring these advantages means giving too much ground to competitors.

It is possible to externally manufacture (or outsource) the activities that do not generate added value, and maintain value-generating activities such as design, logistics, finishing, distribution, service, etc. in the current production centres.

There are many examples in other sectors that efficiently combine the external manufacture and the own manufacture.

In addition, these facilities also become future sales platforms.

This increase in competitiveness is what will save part of the employment in the country of origin.

2.5.1.2 *The "survivor", "local" o "reactive" company*

It is the profile of company that, finds at specialization, differentiation and innovation its own market niche to survive.

These companies pay special attention to costs, to the minimization of stocks and to the speed of response. Many of these companies inevitably resort to import or international subcontracting to be competitive.

Therefore, a proper management of logistics activities is vital in this type of business and, above all, to orientate its efforts towards the search for elements that allow it to differentiate itself from the emerging suppliers of the emerging countries (added value, service, quality, design, greater technical content).

Even from the company itself it is possible to carry out specialized commercial and marketing activities that favour the professionalization and loyalty of the traditional channel.

This type of company benefits from the additional advantages of being located in a cluster and / or industrial district, sometimes even becoming pure trading companies.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.5.1.3 *Need for outsourcing*

In all cases the business models emphasize that in the future, companies in the toy sector will increasingly have less prominence in the production area.

In this way, the competitiveness of the company depends fundamentally on the correct outsourcing, management markets, the construction and efficient management of a global and local network of suppliers and the activities of distribution (logistics), marketing and design. Then, Partner matching is important.

The fundamental factor for reacting successfully is to assume that what is being done so far may not be the right thing to do in the future and that, therefore, a critical attitude with oneself, of assimilation and struggle against change, That sets goals and actions in the medium and long term; In short, to act with "strategy" ²⁵.

On this way, Strategic alliances ²⁶ are undertaken to create value through complementarities of resources and capabilities of the partner firms. Tis Strategic alliances can develop a matching framework to define collaboration.

With this background we are ready to understand the results obtained in the WP1 with the interviews to the companies.

2.5.2 Toy Industries Perspective

From Toy Company point of view, considering that outsourcing strategies just is up to facilities available in each company, we find totally different types of activities, profiles and, at the end, partner matching criteria.

Using as a reference, work (interviews) carried out in WP1 and reflected the results in the deliverable D1.1, we were able to discover the different stages where outsourcing (and partner matching) was needed.

²⁵ Cuervo, A. (1995): "La Dirección Estratégica de la Empresa", en Cuervo (Dir): La Dirección de Empresas de los 90, Ed. Civitas, Madrid, pp. 51-69.

²⁶ Choice, Matching, and Human Behavior: A Review of the Literature W. David Pierce and W. Frank Epling The University of Alberta

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.5.2.1 Preproduction stage

It can be observed in the graph, as in the stage of Preproduction (section 3.3.2 Preproduction Stage), several stakeholders considered outsourcing in this stage:

Figure 2-5 Outsourcing on Preproduction Stage

There is no high subcontracting (i.e. more internal work is done than subcontracted within the company), but above all, the manufacture of prototypes, user testing and the development of prototype moulds are the most outsourced activities.

2.5.2.2 Production stage

In production Stage (3.3.3 Production Stage), several stakeholders identified:

Q. Please indicate which of the following activities are carried out and/or are outsourced by your company in the category selected (multiple choice)

Figure 2-6 Outsourcing on Production Stage

In the production phase there is an increase in subcontracting due to the outsourcing of tasks such as assembly, production and certification of regulations.

Considering that the most frequent process in toy companies is the transformation of plastic (4.1.2 Plastic, additive and / or resin transformation) taking into account the tasks as: injection moulding, blow moulding, thermoforming, machining, additive manufacturing and extrusion. In all cases, the number of companies that outsource this process is higher than those that perform it internally

Most frequent manufacturing processes in plastics, additives and/or resins

(n=37)

SOURCE: AIJU 2017

Q. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding plastics, additives and/or resins

Figure 2-7 Outsourcing on Most frequent Plastic Manufacturing Processes

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.5.2.3 Post-Production Stage

In the post-production stage (3.3.4 Post Production Stage), several stakeholders identified outsourcing in this stage, in almost every task, outsourcing to internal work is exceeded.

Figure 2-8 Outsourcing on Postproduction Stage

In post-manufacturing activities, the most outsourced tasks transport, logistics, product placement and advertisement.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

2.5.3 Key take-aways

Generally, companies in the sector have implemented the ISO-9001: 2015 Quality System, which means that they have a proceeded Supplier Evaluation System.

Two types of supplier selection are generally differentiated: Initial selection process and continually re-evaluating process.

- Initial selection process.

When is the first time to find a new supplier, the criteria are usually based on the search of guarantees that accredit the new supplier. Generally, these guarantees become documents or certificates that validate that the supplier is accredited or complies with the standards to provide certain services or develop certain products. Obviously under equal condition, the costs or quality of the offer is what tips the scales.

- Re-evaluation process

Every year, following the quality criteria, companies enter into the cycle of continually re-evaluating or evaluating their suppliers, for this comes into play factors such as the supplier's response in parameters such as time limit, quality ...

The different criteria used in suppliers' evaluation could be:

- Evaluation by history
- Evaluation or personal interview
- Evaluation by certificates or guarantee
- Evaluation by questionnaires
- Evaluation by quality of the offer or sample testing
- Internal audit

Other criteria that make it possible to choose one supplier or another to carry out certain activities is conditioned by the fulfilment of the environmental requirements.

3 TOYLABS OPEN INNOVATION AND CO-CREATION METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS

3.1 STAKEHOLDERS IDENTIFICATION

Several stakeholders have been identified as potential users of the ToyLabs solution. Table 3-1 gives a description of the profiles which should be considered in the conception of ToyLabs, as was presented in D1.1.

Table 3-1. Stakeholder identification.

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION	VALUE PROPOSITION
Manufacturers	<p>A person, group, or company that owns or runs a manufacturing plant.</p> <p>Companies that are responsible of the whole process of creation a new toy, from its ideation to delivering the toy to the shops.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to produce other people's designs, concepts or ideas Capacity to negotiate spaces in the toy stores through their contacts
Inventors	<p>People or companies that offer new toy ideas, concepts or designs usually to manufacturers or distributors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to create new toy ideas
Designers	<p>People or companies that offer new toy ideas, concepts or designs usually to manufacturers or distributors.</p> <p>Additionally, they can help the evolution of other people's concepts or ideas to designs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to create new toy ideas Capacity to transform ideas into designs
Engineers	<p>People or companies that offer to help with the evolution of conceptual designs into more detailed states with all the information needed for their mass production</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity to turn conceptual designs into more detailed ones with all the information needed for their mass production
User experts	<p>Companies or persons that are experts and have the necessary infrastructure to test</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Degree of appeal Degree of usability Consultancy regarding trend analysis for the

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION	VALUE PROPOSITION
	<p>concepts, designs, prototypes and final products with final users (parents and children usually).</p> <p>The main variables that they use to analyse are: Level of appeal, usability and trend analysis.</p>	<p>generation of new concepts or ideas</p>
Marketers	<p>People or companies who are experts in the promotion of toys. Their main activities are: advertising, social media management, product placement, sales and contact with distributors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advertisement management (creation of TV adverts, catalogues, radio, etc.) • Social Media management
Market and design researchers	<p>People or companies who are experts in the detection of market and user needs. Their expertise is based on the transformation of these insights into new opportunities for the market</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity to identify insights and market gaps • Capacity to transform insights into requirements and new opportunities
Safety experts	<p>People or companies who are experts in analysing and applying all the safety standards that affect the toy industry</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety certification and consultancy of concepts, designs, prototypes and final products
Suppliers	<p>Companies that provide the necessary material, components and/ or machinery required by the manufacturers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass production • Mould creation • Components • Materials
Distributors	<p>Companies that own toy stores or specific spaces for selling toys</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliver the toys to the final users
Lawyers	<p>A person whose profession is to represent clients in a court of law or to advise or act on behalf of them in other legal matters.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide the legal framework to guarantee the correct collaboration of the companies in their sharing of the property rights

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION	VALUE PROPOSITION
FabLabs	A FabLab is an international concept that started at MIT. The term FabLab is an abbreviation from Fabrication Laboratory and it is defined as: a small-scale workshop offering (personal) digital fabrication.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short series and prototype manufacturing

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

3.2 METHODOLOGY DEFINITION

3.2.1 Introduction

In direct correlation with the directives coming from the DoA, the purpose of this chapter is to deliver a methodological framework, that can be used in the hands of any toy manufacturing company and specifically SMEs for attaching more value to their design processes and new product development activities. This is accomplished firstly through the development of a holistic ToyLabs methodology for Open Innovation and Co-creation, that is presented in terms of discrete methodological steps, and, afterwards through the detailed description of the separate, but interdependent, methodological foundations under the notions of “Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis”, “End-user Feedback Acquisition through Augmented Reality” and “Partner Matching and Selection”, that can be seen both as standalone methodologies exploited by any toy manufacturer that wants to achieve a very specific goal but also as modules of a larger methodology that aspires to completely change how toy design is conducted, especially in SMEs.

3.2.2 Open Innovation and Co-creation Holistic Methodology

The ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation Methodology refers to a complete methodological approach developed under the scope of the project’s concept and objectives. The methodology describes all the steps, the interconnections and the flow of information and actions for adopting in practice an open innovation model in the toys’ creation process with the active involvement of multiple stakeholders. Without eliminating other roles, the main stakeholders to which ToyLabs - as a project - and the Open Innovation and Co-creation methodology - as an approach – focuses are:

- Toy Manufacturers
- Fabrication Laboratories (FabLabs)
- Safety Experts/ Environmental Experts
- Childhood Experts
- Market Experts & Representatives (B2B customers & End customers)

In addition to those stakeholders, the methodology also refers to the role of “Product Owner”, which can be any member of the ToyLabs network who has an idea for a new toy and wishes to invest on it. Usually the role of the product owner belongs to a toy manufacturing organization, however there are cases that a FabLab, a Safety Expert or even a childhood expert may have an idea for a new toy and through ToyLabs may try to collaborate with a manufacturer in order to bring this idea to life and to the market. In this case the Product Owner role is being assigned to the originator of the idea, while the manufacturer supports the implementation of the product on the basis of specific contractual agreement made between the product owner and the manufacturer, clarifying the roles and the rights of each party.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

The phases of the ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation methodology, the flow and the interconnections among the phases are presented in the following figure. The whole approach has been based on:

- The industry survey performed and described in D1.1 (WP1)
- The high-level user requirements presented in D1.2 (WP1)
- An extensive literature review work and development of an integrated methodology performed under WP2.

Figure 3-1 ToyLabs Methodology Diagram

The methodology, as presented in the previous diagram and analyzed per phase in the current section, has been inspired by the FITMAN²⁷ Verification & Validation Methodology for the development of software for manufacturing enterprises. In practice, while building on the idea of an enhanced V-Model(ISTQB, 2015), the

²⁷ <http://www.fitman-fi.eu>

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

ToyLabs approach introduces a totally new view as far as it concerns product development in the toy industry. It has to be mentioned, additionally, that with a few modifications the approach could be probably applied in other Creative Industries as well.

In principle, the ToyLabs Open Innovation & Co-creation methodology is based on the fact – which has been also pointed out in WP1 deliverables – that in order to improve the whole product development process it's important to include in the process multiple stakeholders even from the early stages. On the other hand, since for a sector like toys which is addressed to children and teens, having a well-defined approach for validating the end-products is a very crucial and sensitive issue, specific emphasis has been given in utilising different types of product assessment and validation activities, in a way that fits the industry standards and the toy safety issues which are of highest importance.

3.2.2.1 *Immersion*

The immersion phase stands at the beginning of the creation of any new product, especially of those belonging in the creative industries domains. As thoroughly described in D1.1 and D1.2, immersion refers to understanding potential market needs and get inspired in order to create a new product or an improved version of an existing one. In the toy industry domain, this phase does not include designing a new toy – sometimes not even drafting it – but getting inspired about the main characteristics, appearance and features that could lead to a new toy (or to a new/ improved version of a toy).

The most important part of the immersion phase is to make it understand the actual market needs. This can be done by getting the complete picture of the toy's category market under consideration, through listening potential customers and understanding what are the characteristics to be included in a new product in order to increase the possibilities of becoming commercially successful. Large companies in the toy industry do support this phase by spending important amounts of money in several types of market research activities, while sometimes they rely on hiring inventors who have previously proven that they do have deep knowledge of the market. However, for SMEs things are not so easy. Hiring successful toy inventors or designers is not actually an option due to budget issues, while the same stands for buying expensive market research studies. Now, SMEs mostly rely on the inputs that their marketing departments may have directly from existing customers (either B2B or B2C), which only a few times do actually have specific proposals that could become the basis for a new product.

ToyLabs comes to offer to the immersion phase a new possibility for any participating company. Specifically, ToyLabs relies on the wisdom of the crowd, as expressed through Web 2.0 social media channels, in order to collect needs, proposals,

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

characteristics to include or to avoid and even completely new ideas which could serve as a basis for a totally new toy or for an enhanced version of any existing one.

The ToyLabs approach considers that nowadays the social media and in general Web 2.0 channels are valuable sources of data which if they get analysed and processed accordingly, they may offer insights (to be used in immersion phase of a new product) which sometimes cannot be acquired even through professional market research studies. Based on this fact, the ToyLabs open innovation and co-creation holistic methodology incorporates a market trends and social feedback analysis approach about how valuable information and insights that could significantly support the immersion phase for a new or enhanced toy can be extracted or produced. The innovative approach itself is presented in detail in the next section (3.2.3) of the present deliverable.

From the stakeholders' point of view, the ToyLabs approach apart from supporting Toy Manufacturers during the immersion phase, has a wider scope: to pave the way for anyone who has an initial idea for a new toy to explore whether the idea is innovative and if it follows current market trends. For ToyLabs anyone can become the initiator of a new toy product – so the approach described here and thoroughly in the next section doesn't only refer to toy manufacturers but to anyone who has an idea and wishes to identify market trends and needs in order to validate and further improve the idea and even before selecting collaborators from the toy industry to help him/her transform the idea into a product.

3.2.2.2 *Concept Definition*

The concept definition phase of the ToyLabs methodology consists of the required actions for setting up the development of a new toy. Specifically, concept definition begins from deciding and writing down the main characteristics of the product under consideration and finishes with the conceptual design of the toy. The main scope of the ToyLabs approach regarding this phase is to find partners for supporting the realisation of the idea leading not only to the conceptual design of the new product but also to an initial feasibility assessment. In case the owner of the idea (and of the product to be developed) is a toy manufacturer, the concept definition and the immersion phases could be considered as one phase consisting of two activities. On the other hand, for the case that the idea owner doesn't have the all or some of the competences of a toy manufacturer, (e.g. product design skills, feasibility assessment skills, engineering skills etc) the concept definition phase includes the process of finding the most appropriate manufacturer and creating a partnership between the idea owner and the manufacturer. At this stage, it is also agreed and defined how the ownership/property rights of the product to be developed will be shared among the involved parties (usually a toy manufacturer and the owner of the idea for a new toy). This can be any type of agreement: the product owner may keep 100% of the product IPRs or may share them with the manufacturer. At the same time, it is being agreed

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

who is the one who shall manage the next steps of the product development process: it can be the idea/product owner in case he/she has the technical skills to do so, or the manufacturer acting for the product owner.

From a methodological point of view, a product owner can at this phase find and select the most appropriate manufacturer to collaborate by following the methodological steps defined in the ToyLabs Partner Matching and Selection Methodology as described next in Section 3.2.5.

Regarding feasibility assessment, ToyLabs considers that depending on the exact toy sector, the country and the available information, the feasibility check for a new product at the conceptualisation phase is case-specific. The same stands for IPR check in order to verify that there are no conflicts regarding intellectual property issues.

3.2.2.3 *Design*

The design phase includes the development of the detailed design of the new product, including details about materials, engineering and required processing. ToyLabs proposes an enhanced iterative design approach based on collaboration with external parties who belong in the ToyLabs network. Specifically, ToyLabs considers that the initial product design is shared with one or more FabLabs as well as with safety experts in order to provide feedback and recommendations on the design.

The collaborative design approach of ToyLabs considers that for each new product a number of collaborators (normally one or more FabLab(s) and a safety expert) have to be selected at this stage by the product owner/ manufacturer.

The contribution of the FabLabs mostly refers to technical insights regarding the materials, the processing and the technical feasibility of the design, however is not limited to that. Depending on the case and the experience of the design team of the product owner/ manufacturer, the FabLabs may also proceed directly to proposed changes on the design (to be approved by the product owner), or they may transform the 2D designs into 3D. Creating detailed 3D designs is required in order to proceed to the prototyping phase which follows, so at this stage the contribution of the FabLabs can be crucial.

Regarding the workflow of the process, an iterative approach is being adopted. The lead designer of the product owner/ manufacturer shares the initial designs of the new toy and asks from the FabLabs that have been included in the project to provide their feedback, either in general or on specific details of the design. The FabLab(s) may either provide comments or create enhanced versions of the designs and share them back. Afterwards the designer may create a new design incorporating either all or some of the recommended changes and share it again with the involved stakeholders.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

The process continues in an iterative way until the designer or the product owner finalizes the design.

At any time during the above process, as well as after finalizing the design, the product owner may also include in the loop safety experts asking them to provide recommendations regarding the compliance of the design to the safety standards that apply for the specific toy category. Although compliance check is something that can be done only after finalizing the product, the provision of recommendations/ feedback by safety experts at this early stage is considered crucial in the ToyLabs approach in order to reduce costs incurred if any toy-safety related issue is identified at a later stage.

3.2.2.4 *Prototyping*

The scope of prototyping is the product under design to become tangible in order to be assessed by pilot end-users and to get the initial feeling of how the final product will look like and operate. In other words, prototypes are created to simulate the final solution in a way that an end-user can interact with them, and to evaluate them which can be considered as early testing of the actual final product. Prototyping is not, of course a one-off process, but an iterative one: the first prototypes are usually cheap and simple, and tend to evolve into more complex and detailed solutions.

The main characteristics that ToyLabs adds to the (typical) process from a methodological point of view are the following:

- Finding the most appropriate FabLabs in terms of experience and equipment for building the prototypes, through the partner matching methodology as described in Section 3.2.5 of the present deliverable.
- Take advantage of the different locations of the FabLabs in order to build different versions of the prototype in each case, adapted respectively to the local environment, culture or needs – this may be limited to translating any written text to the local language – or to more important radical changes e.g. dolls having different hair or skin color.
- Use an Augmented Reality approach, as described in Section 3.2.4 of the present deliverable for acquiring feedback from groups of experts and end-users on the created prototypes. Taking advantage of Augmented Reality technologies is important for providing to the user / product tester a complete look-and-feel of the prototype which will be as close as possible to the final product.

Prototyping is actually the most important phase regarding the collaboration among Manufacturers – FabLabs – Safety Experts on which the whole open innovation and co-creation concept of ToyLabs is based. Especially as far as it concerns FabLabs,

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

while in the previous phases their role is limited in terms of supporting design and providing feedback to the manufacturers, in the prototyping phase they get the focus of the whole process. After the design of the new toy has been finalised, the product owner/ manufacturer utilises the partner matching and selection approach (see Section 3.2.5) in order to identify which FabLabs – member of ToyLabs network – do have the competencies to create prototypes of the specific toy. After selecting one or more of them (depending on one hand on the cost/ price they offer and on the other hand on whether the product owner is interested to get a partner is a specific country) and proceeding to contractual agreements regarding the services to be offered, the manufacturer provides the designs and the requirements for the prototypes to be developed. The prototypes may be exactly the same for all the FabLabs that have been selected for the specific product or may be different in order to address ‘localised’ versions of the toys in each market.

The next step is the development of the 3D model which is required for producing the prototypes. This is something that both the designers of the manufacturing organisation and the designers of the FabLabs may be able to do, so it’s up to the agreement between the two parties whether the FabLabs shall provide such a service or not. Nevertheless, after agreeing on the 3d designs, one or more prototypes of the toy are being produced by the FabLabs. Depending on the category of the toy product and whether it’s one of the first iterations of prototyping, the produced item may have significant simplifications compared to the designed end-product. These simplifications may refer to appearance issues (e.g. colouring) or to functional/ operational issues (e.g. with less degrees of freedom of the moving parts). This is something expected and absolutely normal and at the same time it is the main reason for involving Augmented Reality technologies in the ToyLabs approach.

Timewise, the Augmented Reality model is being built in parallel with the development of the prototype, the scope of which is when combined with the tangible prototype to offer to the user a look-and-feel as much closer to the look-and-feel of the final product. This way either the FabLab or the Product Owner directly has the opportunity to organise experts/ focus groups, consisting of childhood experts, market experts, end customers (including end users/children if no safety hazards are identified). The scope of this process is to collect feedback from such experts/ focus groups, in order to be sent back to the manufacturer for proceeding to improvements on the toys under development. The whole process may have several iterations leading to new versions of the prototypes each time (and if needed of the AR product-specific solutions), until, based on the feedback received it’s decided which will be the final prototype(s), fully representing the actual end-product version(s) to be sent for manufacturing.

A similar assessment but from the safety standards point of view is being performed by the safety experts in order also to provide insights about things to be changed for conforming to all related International and EU toy safety standards.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Obviously, the iterative prototyping phase of the methodology is the most crucial as through the prototypes and the feedback received, the process may continue to the next phase. The development and assessment of the prototypes by childhood experts, end-users and by safety experts and the utilisation of the AR framework as supposed by the present methodology for competing the experience of potential users.

3.2.2.5 *Pre-production / Pre-series manufacturing*

The scope of the phase is setting up the whole production/ manufacturing process and producing the first series of the product to be used both for assessing it (from a functional and operational scope and from a toy safety point of view) and for getting feedback from market experts in order to build the product's marketing strategy.

All the next steps of the ToyLabs methodology refer to the different types of testing and assessment of the final product, based on the pre-series manufacturing performed.

As far as it concerns this phase, ToyLabs enhances specific parts of the usual process followed by most companies. From the development and assessment of the different prototypes, performed in the previous phase, alternative customised/ localised versions of the same product may have been decided, so the pre-production and pre-series manufacturing of each alternative version of the final product has to be planned.

Furthermore, the experience acquired by the FabLabs and the feedback and technical consultation they may provide, based on the prototyping process (e.g. regarding specific attention that has to be shown for sensitive toy parts), must be taken into account for optimally setting up the pre-production of the product.

3.2.2.6 *Operational Assessment*

The operational assessment is the first step of the ToyLabs product verification and validation process which refers to the actual final product before it gets distributed to the market. The scope is to verify that the end product operates fully as described during its detailed design and fulfils all the functional requirements defined.

In case any inconsistency is identified during this phase (e.g. an operational characteristic which has been described doesn't exist), it has to be examined whether the prototype on which the final item has been based also had the same issue. If this is the case then the whole process gets back to the Prototyping phase in order to further improve and afterwards re-assess the prototype, while a new pre-series manufacturing based on the amended model has to be implemented.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

On the other hand, if the issue does not appear on the developed prototype, then the setup of the production has to be examined (from material selection and mould development up to parts assembly), in order to identify and fix the issue before proceeding to the next phases.

The operational assessment does not involve external parties as the product has to be checked versus its own requirements and detailed design. So the stakeholders involved are the product owner and the manufacturer and the FabLabs for providing production insights based on the developed prototypes

3.2.2.7 *Safety & Environmental Impact Assessment*

The safety and environmental impact assessment refers to the actual validation of the final toy on the basis of International and EU safety and environmental standards. While, during the whole ToyLabs process, consultation and feedback is being provided by safety and environmental experts in several phases of the process, in the present phase all the tests required take place so to confirm that the product has all the safety characteristics in order to get certified based on existing safety standards. As far as it concerns environmental impact assessment, this includes on one hand validating that the product itself including the materials used and the production method applied are in compliance with environmental standards and rules and on the other hand the estimation of the environmental impact of the production process and of the product itself, which is of high value for toy-companies which rely on 'green' strategies and environmental-friendly approaches, also promoting this through their marketing strategy.

In case any issue is identified during this phase, especially if it concerns a hazard and as the toy sector is very sensitive in safety issues, then it has to be examined whether there has been a design flaw as the main reason for the product not passing safety tests or if it's an issue of the production. This is made in collaboration of the manufacturer with the toy safety expert with the support of the involved FabLabs if required. In any case finding and verifying the root of the problem is crucial as the whole process has to get back either to the design phase, if the design itself had issues not earlier identified, or to the phases to follow.

3.2.2.8 *Experts/ End Users Assessment*

The ToyLabs open innovation and co-creation methodology involves experts of the childhood domain early in the process, in order the products to be conceptualised, designed and tested according to the end-user requirements, the market needs and the insights provided by a wide spectrum of childhood professionals. The assessment

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

performed at this stage has as a main scope to collect feedback on the actual final product by:

- Childhood experts, examining the toy from an educational and/or psychological impact view
- End users, testing the toy and providing feedback about its main advantages and disadvantages
- Toy market experts (distributors, wholesalers etc) to provide feedback regarding marketing issues like packaging, product appearance and promotion

At this stage, the feedback received only in very few cases may lead back to previous steps of the process. If the assessment performed has a totally negative outcome, then the product owner has to identify whether the initial concept was out of market or if the way that is has been implemented failed. However, given the fact that the whole process is based on getting feedback during the early phases of product development, this is not considered a possible case. The results of the assessment performed at this phase are crucial mainly as input to the next phase referring to the commercialisation of the product. In other terms to identify and provide tips to be taken into account by the marketing department of the product owner/ manufacturer so that the way that the toy will be promoted to the market to fit its characteristics and to emphasise on its main advantages considered as important for the selection of the toy by the end customer.

3.2.2.9 *Commercialisation*

The ToyLabs methodological approach refers to the development of a toy from its inception to its creation and the setup of its production. The commercialisation process mostly refers to the marketing and sales operations which are not covered by the ToyLabs lifecycle. The scope of the ToyLabs process however is to provide to the marketing experts the results of multiple types of evaluation of the product, regarding safety, environmental impact, educational value, main advantages etc, in order this information to be combined and taken into account for building the product's marketing strategy. For ToyLabs what is crucial at this phase is to setup a mechanism for collecting feedback from end-users/ customers in a well-structured way. The feedback collected will be taken into account not for the product itself (as it's already in the market) but during the immersion and conceptualisation phases either for any toy belonging in the same category or for developing an updated/ enhanced version of an existing toy, taking into account the good and the bad feedback reports of the version already in the market.

3.2.3 Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis Methodology

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

The ToyLabs methodology “Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis” refers to the identification of market trends as these may emerge through an analysis of the online activity of users (i.e. prospective customers) as well as the efficient management and analysis of the feedback that arises for a specific company through the user mentions of the brand or its products/services in the web.

Therefore, **two different flows** can be recognised and should be handled by this methodology and these are as follows:

- 1) One flow for **feedback management and analysis** of a selected brand/product/competitor/etc.
- 2) One flow for **trend detection and analysis** for a specific domain of interest (e.g. dolls, puzzles, etc.).

Broader data sources and larger stakeholder pools are thus being considered as relevant with the toy industry and the design of new toys and are being integrated into the proposed methodology in an attempt to on the one hand gain insights into the expected adoption of a new toy design by a somewhat uninvolved crowd, i.e. a diverse crowd that was not specifically questioned to provide opinions on specific ideas, as is the case for the End Customers engaged in the ToyLabs Open Innovation platform, and on the other hand early identify any issues or customers disapproval/dissatisfaction for their current products.

In that view, six core steps are being identified, that have a direct correlation with the steps and processes identified from the landscape analysis, as well as one preparatory step, step 0, that is a step performed outside the platform among the involved stakeholders in order to configure the analysis to follow to their specific needs and their industry’s specific characteristics.

The following figure presents the high-level scope of the processes to be implemented in the context of the methodology, while each step will be thoroughly described in the subsequent sections.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Figure 3-2 Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis Methodology in steps

3.2.3.1 Preparatory step - Step 0

As already mentioned, this step is responsible for analysing the needs of the toy manufacturer in question and customise/adapt the analysis that follows according to the industry/product type he represents. In that view, the following decisions have to take place in the context of this step:

- Decision on the social media accounts to be tracked: Firstly, the exact social media platforms to be examined have to be decided. Twitter and Facebook are the ones that have been mostly met in the dedicated literature review section and have a proven power with regard to their use to extract trends and insights from crowd wisdom. Therefore, these are the social media platforms to proceed with during the 1st iteration of the ToyLabs methodology. However, not both platforms may interest the toy manufacturers on each specific case or different weights may be considered for each one of them depending on the case in question. Furthermore, specific accounts of influencers of the examined domain or accounts that the toy manufacturer in question considers as most relevant and interesting have to be selected during this preparatory step.
- Integration on the analysis of the blogs/Portals of the toy industry that the company is interested in monitoring. Although rare in certain manufacturing domains, the existence of dedicated portals, blogs or even wikis should not be overlooked, as it offers targeted information, i.e. less noisy than generic social media platforms, from people that are experts or, at least, interested in the domain. Influential blogposts, vivid discussions and buzz created around a new or existing toy – or even anything that could be afterwards translated into a toy (e.g. animation movie characters) - can act as a first-line trend detection or insights for the approval of a new toy.
- Selection of specific keywords (or hashtags in the “social media language”) to be used as search terms. Each selected key-phrase/term should correspond to

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

a company's product, toy category or a new design idea for a toy in order to support collecting only relevant information from the selected sources and acquire time-wisely and effortlessly feedback for these terms/ideas and/or identify trends about the broader categories that these terms are representing.

- Decision on the languages of interest. On certain cases, the language of the text (comments, posts, tweets, etc.) to be retrieved may play a significant role according to the nature of the manufacturing company in question, its location etc.

Other sources to be considered for integration in the methodology to extract trends and acquire and analyse feedback could be feedback forms, since they guarantee relativeness with the toy category and their source is specific and reliable. Positive feedback may serve as validation of existing toy design ideas, whereas negative feedback and complaints can serve as seeds to identify needs that can then be used to get inspiration for new toys, to refine existing ideas towards specific directions and to broaden other ideas to include implied requirements. However, their integration or not depends on the toy manufacturer/owner that runs the analysis, as well as the availability or not of such feedback forms to be processed.

3.2.3.2 *Data Collection – Step 1*

Having made all the necessary configurations and decisions on the appropriate key-phrases to initiate the search, the sources to look into etc., this step is responsible for data retrieval and storage. In this context, data collection is based on the settings of the previous step where identified search keywords, known user accounts of the domain and preselected blogs are determining the data to be retrieved.

This is a process that usually does not include any significant technical challenges, since on each specific source there are usually standard approaches to implement that. Concerning social media sources, the most popular social media platforms offer APIs that allow 3rd party application developers to access their content. This is usually done for free. The only difficulty that may arise have to do with rate limits that may apply on certain cases. Regarding blogs and portals, data retrieval is easily accomplished using configured web crawlers.

There is only one controversial issue regarding this step that needs to be tackled and it has to do with the decision on the time period for the data retrieval, in order to reduce to the extent that is possible unnecessary burden from the retrieval of data that are outdated. This decision has to do with an issue that is greatly researched in the academic literature, under the field of Social Network Analysis, dealing with the life span of expressed opinions and the timing and the way they were formulated in order to leverage the special characteristics of each social platform.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

3.2.3.3 *Data pre-processing step – Step 2*

The purpose of this step is to homogenise the diverse input types coming from different social media platforms, blogs, portals etc. giving as output all gathered data in the form of tuples that carry the following attributes:

- The core textual part of each main piece of data
- The stakeholder, i.e. the opinion holder
- The time that each piece of data was published
- The source of the retrieved data (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)
- The importance indicator: This is an additional indicator specifically employed to measure the text importance and influential power of the given text extracted from source-specific information that will be excluded from the next processing step. Depending on the source the way this indicator will be measured may vary significantly. In the context of ToyLabs, when dealing with social media sources, an influencer identification algorithm will be applied as a first importance indicator to outline the expected impact of a given piece of information. A combination of features will be measured for that purpose, related both with the opinion holder and the posts themselves (e.g. number of followers and number of retweets for the Twitter's case). For blog posts and portals, properties indicating the discussion's liveliness, such as the length of comments, their number and the discussion growth rate, will define the importance indicator.

It needs to be noted that, although certain initial guidelines have been given for the measurement of the importance indicator, further research can be implemented since its complexity and popularity in the social network analysis field have rendered it an active, standalone research area.

Apart from that a first-level filtering is also expected as part of this step, to remove noise. For example, depending on the case, promotional marketing content may be considered as such. Removal of malicious content is also envisaged. Furthermore, text sanitisation may be part of this pre-processing step, namely the process of locating and removing sensitive data from a set or database.

3.2.3.4 *Data processing step – Step 3*

Data processing step is responsible for converting the text that expresses an opinion, an idea and consecutively a potential trend in an appropriate representation for the analysis that will follow in the next steps. Towards this end, linguistic processing has to be employed, where a number of NLP techniques should be applied in order to transform unstructured text into vectors. In Table 2-3 of section 2.3.2, several linguistic processing techniques were referenced as part of the approach/methodology proposed for trends detection by the studied papers. These techniques, as well as other common techniques encountered in the literature, are explained in brief along the following lines to demonstrate their relevance and the reason behind their proposed usage:

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- **Tokenisation:** It is the process of substituting a sensitive data element with a non-sensitive equivalent, which is referred to as token that has no exploitative meaning or value²⁸. Tokenising a piece of text is usually the first step in order to transform it into structured information. Every natural language processing library/toolkit contains it. For European languages, tokenisation is generally straightforward.
- **Stop-words removal:** Stop words usually refer to the most common words in a language, such as “and”, “or” etc. However, there is not a universal approach about which word is a stop word and which one is not. Therefore, different stop words lists can be found, more or less strict, and be applied according to the case.
- **Repeated character removal:** It filters out noise from the examined piece of information and it can be accomplished in varying levels of intensity and depth, ranging from basic, simple removal of more than N appearances of the same character to smarter techniques.
- **Special characters removal or replacement:** This technique applies especially in the case of social media where written language follows different rules, e.g. the use of the @ sign, of hashtags and abbreviations. These specific characters may, however, depending on the case, encapsulate useful information that should be captured, but this can be done through their indirect integration into other attributes, such as the importance indicator introduced in the previous section.
- **POS Tagging:** POS tagging, namely the process of marking up a word in a corpus as corresponding to a particular part of speech, has been greatly documented in the academic literature and there are plenty of available libraries to support this process.
- **Normalisation:** This technique has to do with all actions to correct any evident mistakes of the use of a word and ensure that they are not being passed by to the final vector, increasing the vector’s dimensionality without reason (e.g. use of slightly different versions of the same word) as well as that data from different sources are being presented under a common model.
- **Stemming:** Every natural language processing library provides stemming algorithms, i.e. algorithms to reduce inflected (or sometimes derived) words to their word stem.
- **N-gram:** It is a common phenomenon for a word having different meaning when combined with other words. For that reason, creating n-grams to combine neighbouring words into larger text blocks may help in capturing the actual essence of a piece of text.
- **NER (Named Entity Recognition):** It is a process responsible for classifying named entities in text into pre-defined categories such as the name of a person or a location and it can be really significant in the case of ToyLabs since it may allow identification and mapping of different references to the same entity (e.g. a brand or a product category) and link data from different sources into semantically enriched representations.

²⁸ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tokenization_\(data_security\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tokenization_(data_security))

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

It needs to be noted that it is not mandatory for all the proposed techniques to be applied on all cases. Decision has to be made, depending on the source of information and the specific characteristics of the given case, on the ones to be applied. The final target of all these techniques is to create the features that will serve as vector dimensions to transform the initial text into representative vectors.

Apart from these common and well-represented in the academic literature linguistic techniques for Natural Language Processing of textual input, other ad-hoc technique can be applied, depending on the specific characteristics of the communication mean in question, in order to further filter the given text and come up with its best representation in the vector space.

Indicative examples of such processing techniques -that could either be at a text items level or at a post-level- are:

- Hashtag extraction or removal (especially applied in Twitter): Depending on the methodological needs, hashtags may be desirable and be given specific attention or they may be considered unnecessary and be removed.
- Html elements removal.
- Exclusion of textual inputs that do not meet certain criteria according to the requirements of the methodology. Such examples could be: exclusion of posts with fewer than one predefined number of words, exclusion of posts that use a lot of symbols, exclusion of unlabelled posts (e.g. without hashtags).
- Exclusion of retweets (for Twitter).
- GEO tagging at posts.
- Sorting of posts based on the time of their appearance.

It is up to the decision maker (e.g. the toy manufacturer/owner) to decide on the ones to be applied but in most cases some experimentation have to precede on the type of data for the given industry to come up with a conclusion of their best combination.

3.2.3.5 *Step 4a: 1st-level analysis/ Topic Detection step*

Topic detection, together with the trend detection, which is the next step, are the two most important steps in a trend detection methodology. As mentioned above, they can either be seen separately and be implemented one after the other or they can be implemented in parallel as one step, and this is the case in many cases where topics that are directly traced are popular topics, i.e. trends (e.g. grouping of popular keywords into themes).

In the case of ToyLabs, it is suggested not to take a binding decision either from the one or the other direction, since it is a matter of the data that are being processed to define which is the best one and this can be only decided through experimentation, since the literature does not provide any specific directions and there is multitude of different approaches.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

However, there are two high-level categories of processes that can be identified as part of the topic detection step, when this is dealt with separately from trend detection:

- Use of Topic model algorithms: As already described, topic model algorithms are being used in social media data to define the main topic of the examined posts. From the available algorithms, LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation) (Viégas, Golder, & Donath, 2006; F. Wei et al., 2010) will be used in the context of ToyLabs since it is one of the most important and latest probabilistic models used to detect the hidden topic in a collection of files. It also has the advantage of being used successfully to detect the topic regardless of the data source. It can be used equally in blog posts, articles and social media posts.
- Clustering in broader topics/categories: After identifying the topic of the posts their clustering into broader topics in order to detect hidden similarities/correlations among identified topics should take place. A combination of the clustering methods pointed out in the state-of-the-art analysis in section 2.3.2 is recommended to be used in this step, based on each specific case (e.g. keyword clustering and clustering based on co-occurrences).

3.2.3.6 *Step 4b: 2nd-level analysis/ Trend detection step*

For the trend detection step in the context of ToyLabs, only the two out of the three methodological flows identified and described in the literature analysis that preceded will be examined, namely either the co-existence of the topic and the trend detection step or their treatment separately where topic detection precedes. The first flow where topic detection step is surpassed will not be considered here since its processes are more complicated without providing proven better results.

Without excluding other options, specific attention will be given in the separate treatment of the two steps, topic and trend detection, since it is giving the opportunity to better monitor the corresponding processes and interfere manually when needed, in the sense that totally automatic processes usually are not the best option since the human factor can unveil new insights, unseen by most of the available algorithms.

For this selected flow, **statistical monitoring of the identified topics over time comparing them with previous periods** will ensure capturing of the emerging topics, while a novel approach will be also introduced in the context of **statistical analysis and parameter computation** that has to do with the **identification of influencers** of a specific domain of interest.

Influencer identification is a broad research area, especially in the complex structures of modern social media networks. In the context of ToyLabs, it will be used as a weighting strategy that will help toy manufacturers and other interested parties understand how important a particular opinion is. In that view, influencer identification aims to provide answers to the questions: “How much value does this opinion have? How much is it expected to influence others?”.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

It needs to be stressed that how influential an individual is not independent of the community. An influencer that appears to have strong influence on a specific community, might constitute a common entity in a different one. Towards this end, identifying influencers for a specific domain and community might be a challenging task but really prosperous, since it takes into account the specific characteristics of the domain in question. Furthermore, there are different types of influencers ranging from role models (common in fashion industries, as well as in cases of celebrities), communicants (i.e. the individual who initially spreads the information, common in journalists and reporters), reviewers (i.e. people that acquire and comment on a product in order to influence potential future buyers), etc.

Identification of the influencing power of a specific entity is usually done through attributes measuring. There are a lot of different definitions for an influencer and each of the definition calls for different attributes measuring. Therefore, “people who are often mentioned in other people's discussions”, “people whose expressed opinions are commonly referenced by others”, “people whose expressed opinions are widely adopted and liked” and “people who are popular in a network” are just some ways to define an influencer that can be measured through the number of mentions to his name/entity, the number of retweets, the number of likes/favourites and the number of total connections (e.g. followers for Twitter) respectively.

Furthermore, it should be also stressed that each social channel asks for different influence observation techniques. As an example, when dealing with blogs, the goal is to effectively identify influential bloggers; this usually means individuals who are recognised by others, whose activities result in follow-up activities, who have novel perspectives and are eloquent (Keller & Berry, 2003). On the contrary, for Twitter, a more content-oriented approach is usually followed. Number of followers is an important metric but it is not the only one; number of mentions and number of retweets of tweets play an equally important role (Cha, Haddai, Benevenuto, & Gummadi, 2010).

It is important to clarify that when referring to feedback management for an existing product, the trend detection step is passed by and the methodology progresses with the next step, sentiment analysis.

3.2.3.7 *Step 5: 3rd-level analysis/ Sentiment analysis step*

Last step of the methodology has to do with the application of sentiment analysis on the selected trending topics. As seen in the desk research of section 2.3.2, sentiment analysis is not common in trend analysis approaches. However, in the context of ToyLabs, differentiation from the standard approaches is decided providing an innovative approach where the selected trending topics are also analysed regarding the sentiment they encapsulate to identify the ones that are being discussed in a positive way (while also capturing the intensity of the sentiment) in order to detect the trends that are worth considering for potential future toy designs. In cases where

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

the methodology presented is being utilised to acquire feedback for a brand and its product, this step is even more a substantial one, in the sense that concluding to an aggregated sentiment for a “topic” that will represent a specific product, a brand or anything else which the toy manufacturer in question wants to monitor will actually provide the manufacturer with an easily digestible insight on his customers’ perception about the selected subject.

Namely, the proposed methodology aims through this step to achieve two goals:

- To enable the possibility of two different flows, i.e. one for feedback management and analysis and one for trend detection and analysis for a specific domain of interest, through one methodology.
- To further enhance the trend detection flow with an additional step that informs the user not only that a topic is a trending one but also whether it should serve as an inspiration for new toy designs or as a counter-example notifying him of what he should avoid.

Towards this end, customer sentiment should be identified in multiple data sources and be associated with specific product/toy features in order to be transformed into trends or new and improved design ideas.

As a first step, it is important to clarify how sentiment will be measured. In the context of ToyLabs, an approach closer to (Wu & Liang, 2011) and (Busso et al., 2004), as described in the literature review section and in particular section 2.3.2.2, will be employed, namely sentiment will be able to take one from four different values; anger, sadness, happiness and neutral.

Following with a more fine-grained analysis of the process to be followed for this step, **feature-level, aspect-based sentiment analysis** will be employed, a decision justified also by the literature review. According to this approach, a more fine-grained text analysis is performed, emphasising on the opinion/sentiment target, aiming at giving explicit insights into what the opinion holder liked or disliked instead of attributing a positive or a negative sentiment in a whole language construct (i.e. document, paragraph, sentence or phrase). What an aspect could be will be decided upon experimentation with true data on the toy industry domain and specifically the two ToyLabs pilot cases to be developed and tested during the next months of the project under WP5 activities. An example for an aspect, when dealing with a specific product/toy, could be its design, its resistance, its quality, the joy it offers to its users, or whatever else that can be identified as an aspect/concept discussed by the social media users when referring to this product, which can be also affectively annotated.

With regard to the sentiment analysis method to be applied, one of the two following options can be considered:

- **Supervised machine learning** in cases where both the type of data and the expected system users can support the creation of a training dataset.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- **Unsupervised machine learning** in cases where the creation of a training dataset is not possible.

It should be noted, though, that although supervised machine learning is, without doubt, the proposed sentiment analysis method (especially in social media data), providing more accurate results according to literature review, it is also difficult to be applied in real environments since it presupposes a well-defined, adequately big training dataset that calls for a lot of time and effort to be formed. Furthermore, the way the language and terminology that is being used in social media constantly evolves poses additional difficulties. For that purpose, unsupervised sentiment analysis techniques can be considered in combination with statistical keyword extraction and predefined key-phrases detection, in the cases where creation and maintenance of a training dataset is not possible.

Each of these options is combined with lexicon- and rule-based (i.e. application of linguistic rules) approaches, if feasible, following the directives provided by the academic literature that highlights the great value, and the benefits that emerge from the application of combined methods and models. Rule-based methods, in particular, have been proven to be really beneficial in sentiment analysis, when complementing other main methods, especially when they are representing expert knowledge regarding patterns on domain discussions (e.g. syntax patterns for customers writing complaint letters).

Furthermore, it needs to be stressed that domain and sentiment lexicons should be also applied to further enhance the method's results. Their inclusion is imposed by many different factors, such as the diverse nature of the problem- that stems from the fact that the methodology should be applied for any interested toy manufacturer, regardless of his specific expertise -, the variety of sources considered, the diverse maturity level of the selected manufacturing domain regarding its ability to provide the necessary lexical and semantic resources, time availability and effort devotion for their construction and fine-tuning, etc.

From a technical perspective, all these methods and processes defined above can be implemented in a variety of programming languages, while also having the opportunity to choose among a variety of libraries, toolkits and APIs (e.g. Python's NLTK and SciPy for natural language processing and machine learning processes).

3.2.3.8 *Conclusion-Discover Actionable Insights*

Concluding, after the last step (i.e. Step 5) of the methodology, the opportunity is being given to the system's user to discover new, previously hidden insights both about trends in the toy industry and their customers' feeling on their products and brand in order to denature both information into new, innovative, customer-centric toy designs.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Therefore, the current methodology targets directly a toy manufacturing design team and it is important that actionable insights are being given to them. Generic conclusions about crowd satisfaction or dissatisfaction or indications about general trending topics in the form of plain, unconnected words may be totally non-exploitable by them or “painful” to transform them into useful knowledge. For that reason, specific attention should be given on ways to offer **combined insights into the data** that were retrieved, processed and deduced during the previous steps. Sound visual analytics methods will be leveraged smartly, for that part, to model and structure appropriately the representation of the topics, trends and sentiments inferred, along with information regarding their sources, their location and timing characteristics, the importance level attributed to each one of them and any other available contextual information. Analytical goals include among other things overviewing of the latent topics discussed in the social media sources that are being monitored, comparison among these topics and their sentiments to extract and predict trends for a specific toy industry domain, pattern analysis and hidden correlations discovery, understanding of changes over time on short, medium and long term perspective, etc.

Data representation is the cornerstone of visual analytics and its power should not be neglected, since all statistical computations, reasoning methods and algorithms implemented during the previous steps are only gaining actual, actionable value through the right representations that enable finally decision making.

It needs to be emphasised that the methodology that preceded aimed at delineating and cleaning up the market trends and social feedback landscape with a view to the toy industry and provide an initial structure in the form of diverse, solid steps along with specific guidelines –respectful of the literature review results– regarding the methods and techniques to be applied on each one of them. However, these methods and techniques will become further precise during the next months of the project where more experimentation on real datasets retrieved and processed for the two ToyLabs pilot cases will take place enabling better understanding of the special characteristics of the toy industry with regard to the social media use. Therefore, the development of a more informed and even more clear-cut methodology for Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis for the toy industry will be then possible and will be documented, as an update of the present deliverable, in the context of D2.2 on M13.

3.2.4 End-user Feedback Acquisition through Augmented Reality

As mentioned in the project’s DoA, *“a Toy Manufacturer will be able to collect multi-source feedback on new product concepts and designs, through iterative cycles where the initial idea is firstly co-designed with FabLabs, validated by Toy Safety/Certification experts and evaluated by prospective customers both virtually (via Augmented Reality technologies) and actually (based on product prototypes)”*. The following figure depicts the intervention points of Augmented Reality in the TOYLABS

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Toy Creation cycle and suggests also the user groups who will provide feedback, which could be experts, selected end-users, as well as ordinary end users who can see not only augmented prototypes of toys, but also final, market-available versions of already produced toys.

Using this approach, TOYLABS incorporates in the product co-creation process a set of Augmented Reality techniques for acquiring a more complete end-customer feedback and related recommendations for improving new product designs. As discussed previously, whether the toy itself will utilise Augmented Reality characteristics is not a fact depending on TOYLABS, however the utilisation of such emerging and trending technologies within the toy development framework is expected to further increase the interest of the end-customers to become members of the TOYLABS network focus groups.

It needs to be noted that the Augmented Reality feedback generation methodology takes into full account aspects of personal data protection and privacy of end users profile information, as this is pivotal to ensure trust in the platform and in any feedback generation mechanism in general, unless there is a clear intention of a user to reveal his identity during the feedback authoring. Therefore, the activities to be performed from the user's side can be categorised as:

- I. Fully Anonymised Feedback, without the intervention of the TOYLABS platform. This case is applicable only when feedback can be provided without the requirement of a user to be logged in to the platform. In this case, no identity information is recorded and feedback is retrieved fully anonymised.
- II. Pseudo-Anonymised Feedback by the TOYLABS platform. In this case, feedback is requested by users of the platform (e.g. registered and logged in users) and the platform holds the information about their identify, based on the information they have provided in their profile. However, any information that is passed to the initiator of the feedback (such as the manufacturer) is anonymised and no personal information is disclosed. The advantage of this feedback category over the fully anonymised one is the possibility to provide certain obfuscated statistics about the responders of the questionnaires, which can be linked to the answers as well, but that are not in apposition to link back to the real identity of a user. Thus, questionnaire owners are provided with added value information (such as generalised demographics, etc.). alongside with the basic replies to the questions they pose, allowing them to extract better insights.
- III. Named Feedback. In this case, a user working on a questionnaire agrees to reveal his identity, therefore all feedback is provided to the questionnaire owner together with the profile information of the responder.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

The three categories above are both subject of the selection of the questionnaire owner, as well as of the end user. Initially, the questionnaire owner can specify which feedback categories of the above he is willing to accept, and in turn the end user agrees to participate in this feedback request, by selecting the feedback categories permitted by the owner. As such, the latter is able to refuse to participate in case he does not want to provide any personal information to a “Named” feedback request, or agree to participate in case the owner also accepts “Pseudo-Anonymised” feedback.

3.2.4.1 Steps

The exact methodological steps to introduce the Augmented Reality module into the overall validation process offered by the TOYLABS platform, as shown in the next figure are:

Figure 3-3 “Augmented Reality as a Feedback channel” deployment methodology

3.2.4.2 Augmented Reality Model Creation/Refinement

This step actually deals with the uploading of an already designed Augmented Reality model and placeholder in the TOYLABS platform. Considered as the first step of the lifecycle of using Augmented Reality as part of TOYLABS to acquire end user feedback, this step initiates the whole process on the TOYLABS platform and takes as a prerequisite that an Augmented Reality model already exists and is ready to be transferred to the platform. In this context, the platform will provide a designated space that will be used by creators of Augmented Reality models (usually those are the

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

manufacturers or the FabLabs) to upload their designs and describe them, in order to document the information, they would like to display to potential users, besides the Augmented Reality model itself. During this step, the Augmented Reality creator will be in a position to download a simple guide regarding the use of Augmented Reality in TOYLABS, to guide him during the Augmented Reality creation process, pinpointing the supported by the platform formats, specific things that have to be taken under consideration that regard the model itself, as well as some terms of use that would be automatically accepted upon uploading a model into the platform. Moreover, the guide will also include a description of the features that are available in the platform regarding feedback capturing, so that the Augmented Reality creator would be in a better position to generate his model to make the best out of the feedback collection mechanisms available.

3.2.4.3 *Feedback Mechanisms Selection*

Upon uploading an Augmented Reality model, the manufacturer/FabLabs is then tasked to select out of a simple set of feedback features that will be linked with the model. The aim of this step is to provide to the manufacturer a list of predefined feedback tools (such as comments/posts, small questionnaires, rating buttons) that he could choose to accompany his model with questions that he would like to ask. The tools to be provided should allow both structured and unstructured input by end users (e.g. text as well as selections of predefined answers), and special attention should be given to both select the most appropriate tool, as well as to constrain the number of questions and of the available answers towards easing the user experience (thus long textual questions as well as the expectancy of long answers is something that is strongly advice against).

3.2.4.4 *Feedback Questionnaire Generation*

Step 3 of the whole processes deals with the generation of the content of the questions to be asked to users and to be linked to the feedback mechanism and eventually to the Augmented Reality model. To this end, the questionnaire owner goes on and populates the selected from the previous step tools with questions, providing also the possible answers in case those relate to structured feedback tools.

3.2.4.5 *Presentation and Triggering Method Selection*

Once the selection of the questions is finalised, the questionnaire owner is able to select the presentation triggering method to allow the rendering of the models on the users devises. As such, the questionnaire owner would be able to generate a QR code that will be used to trigger the Augmented Reality player in Alternatively other options to trigger the Augmented Reality player could be selected, such as a URL or some buttons that the user might select.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

3.2.4.6 *Enhanced Augmented Reality Model Deployment*

This is the pre-final step of the whole process and deals with the actual finalisation of the Augmented Reality feedback setup in the platform and the actual deployment of the model and of the selected feedback tool on the platform. During this step, the platform is populated with all the latest changes and makes public to the addressed users both the Augmented Reality model as well as the accompanying questionnaire, while in the case of companion mobile Apps that can handle the Augmented Reality view, special tokens are created to be able to link the uploaded material to the mobile App database.

3.2.4.7 *Feedback Acquisition and Analysis*

This is the last step of the methodology's cycle and is the actual provision of the feedback to the manufacturer/FabLab and all interested parties. This step relies on the transposition of the answers retrieved through the questionnaires into both long textual descriptions that derive out of the unstructured commented posted by the users on the platform, as well as in simple charts that are able to showcase the preference of the user. During the provision of the feedback, anonymised statistics are provided, in order to guarantee the privacy and the non-exposure of sensitive data of users. However, those anonymised data include certain obfuscated profile information (like country, age group, genders, etc.), that are able to provide enhanced information to manufacturers/FabLabs, without compromising the real identity of users. Furthermore, at this stage, in case end users have agreed to reveal their identities, more detailed information is provided to the manufacturers, such as specific user profiles and demographics, and manufacturers/FabLabs have the option to directly contact users through the platform.

It needs to be noted that before the initial step, the platform will cater for the provision to the Augmented Reality model creator (Toy Manufacturer and FabLab) of a set of instruction to construct and deliver low cost 3D models for Augmented Reality, able to be displayed with the TOYLABS Augmented Reality player.

As part of the WP3 activities, the consortium will work to refine the proposed methodology from a technological point of view and select the most appropriate Augmented Reality framework to implement the component. Moreover, a client interface will be also provided to allow manufacturers to connect with end-users and gather the opinions of the latter with the help of a more advanced and evident based prototype display method.

3.2.5 Partner Matching and Selection Methodology

The Partner Matching and Selection component of the ToyLabs Open Innovation Model and Co-creation Methodology targets apparently to provide the means for selecting the right stakeholders for a particular project with regard to the creation of a

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

new or improved toy. Thus, it specifies, organises and models the criteria, based on which potential partners are to be selected, whereas it further outlines the techniques and methods, according to which these criteria are synthesised and prioritised, thereby lending preference to one or the other candidate partner. Along these lines, the Partner Matching and Selection Methodology can be decomposed into two parts:

- The identification, definition and classification of the parameters and factors (criteria), required for evaluating the suitability of different candidate partners to undertake certain steps of the ToyLabs Co-creation Methodology (partner matching).
- The specification of the concepts, methods and algorithms, required for making comparisons among candidate partners and selecting the ones that best cover the given requirements (partner selection).

Partner matching relies in the context of the ToyLabs project on a model-based approach (ToyLabs Blueprint Model) that allows to manage and inter-link toy, partner, toy co-creation step and technical capabilities' information, whereas partner selection makes up a multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) task that is addressed through AHP, an appropriate MCDM method.

Attention is drawn to the fact that Partner Matching and Selection is not a one and out process, but enters into several steps of the ToyLabs Methodology, involving different types of partners, as follows:

- During the Design phase, the Partner Matching and Selection component enters with the view to identify
 - *FabLabs* for providing technical insights on the materials to be used and assessing in general the technical feasibility of the envisaged toy design,
 - as well as *Toy Safety experts* for ensuring compliance with safety standards.
- Then, during the Development phase, it comes forward in order to identify
 - the *FabLabs* that will produce the relevant prototypes,
 - as well as *members of the ToyLabs Special Interest Group* that are to provide feedback on the latter.
- Finally, during the Pre-production phase the Partner Matching and Selection component is employed with the goal to identify
 - *Toy Safety experts* for pre-certifying the product prototype or further providing recommendations for its improvement,
 - *Environmental experts* for providing advice on reducing the environmental impact of the production and

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- *FabLabs* for prototyping toy localised versions.

The specifics of the ToyLabs Partner Matching and Selection methodology are described at greater detail in the following paragraphs.

3.2.5.1 *Partner Matching*

Partner matching consists, as already described above, in the specification of the criteria that are necessary for evaluating the suitability of various actors to participate in the ToyLabs Co-creation Methodology. The identification of these criteria has taken place with the contribution of all project partners by means of both face-to-face meetings and discussions that served at eliciting a set of high level requirements, as well as structured questionnaires. The latter were additionally employed to further enrich and refine the feedback originally obtained and to help develop the ToyLabs Blueprint Model, a model-based approach, inspired by and based upon the research work conducted in the context of the IMAGINE²⁹ project, to manage and inter-link partner, toy and technical capabilities' data and information and, in general, help meet the requirements of the entire toy co-creation process.

Along the above lines, the starting point for the specification of the criteria, required for matching partners with toy creation requirements, has been found in the identification of the various stakeholders' potential involvement in each step of the co-creation process. The latter has been elicited by gathering information on the consortium members' intentions of outsourcing specific activities of the toy creation process to external partners, as well as on the type of partners required in each case. Table 3-2 below summarises the perspectives of engagement of different actors in the ToyLabs Co-creation process.

Table 3-2. Partners' potential involvement in the ToyLabs Co-creation process

Activity ³⁰	Manufacturers	FabLabs	Safety Experts	Environmental Experts	Childhood Experts
<i>Conceptualisation phase</i>					
Idea Generation and Concept Definition					X

²⁹ IMAGINE – Innovative end-to-end Management of Dynamic Manufacturing Networks, <http://www.imagine-future-factory.eu/index.dlg>

³⁰ Activities concern only the pre-production stage, as indicated in D1.1, Table 1 (page 27)

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

Product Design	X	X			X
Product Development	X	X	X	X	
Prototype Development	X	X	X		
<i>Design phase</i>					
Product Engineering	X	X			
Mould Development	X				
Safety Certification	X		X	X	X
Users Validation					X

The partner selection criteria brought up by ToyLabs partners generally enumerated parameters, such as the potential partners' location, the types of products produced or respectively the types of services offered, economic factors, such as the man-hour costs or the availability of product pricelists, the certifications and qualifications possessed, technical capabilities and equipment related parameters, as well as the factors of area of expertise and previous experience acquired. These high-level criteria have been subsequently analysed into lesser relevant aspects, providing thus the contents (individual fields) of the ToyLabs Blueprint Model.

A set of key recommendations, generated through extended discussions with the project partners have further been instrumental in helping shape the ToyLabs Blueprint Model. These recommendations have been used as requirements for improving the structure and contents of the ToyLabs blueprints and are as shown in Table 3-3.

Table 3-3. Blueprint Model Requirements

<p>The Blueprint Model should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... provide a low cost method to collect partner and toy-related information ... allow fast and effective partner selection

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

... imprint the profile of different types of partners (e.g. companies/organisations, individuals)

- ... enable partner authentication and certification
- ... include information on partners' reputation and inspire trust
- ... allow SLA establishment
- ... include historical information (e.g. track record)
- ... include technical capabilities and equipment related information
- ... provide up-to-date partner information
- ... provide support during the whole toy co-creation process
- ... provide understanding of the technical, material, time and cost, safety and environmental compliance requirements for a particular toy
- ... associate partner information with toy requirements information
- ... ensure compliance with toy manufacturing and toy safety standards (?)
- ... include variant parts that capture the characteristics of toy localised versions
- ... allow partners to capture and share core information on toy designs, prototypes, etc.
- ... provide up-to-date information with regard to the status of toy creation process

The ToyLabs Blueprint Model

The ToyLabs Blueprint Model is an information meta-model that targets to support partner selection and improve decision making regarding the toy co-creation process, thus leading to minimising failure rates and shrinking development times for new toys, while also allowing toy manufacturing firms to respond early to market trends and customisation needs and compete larger companies on an equal basis. The key purpose of the ToyLabs Blueprint Model is to accumulate and organise the knowledge needed to help manage the toy co-creation process, match toy requirements with partner characteristics and capabilities, manage partner relationships, and ensure compliance with safety and environmental regulations.

The Blueprint Model provides for unrestricted specification of individual components for different aspects of the toy manufacturing process, and allows the creation of user-specific variant blueprints, where each component can be created

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

with default values, which can later be modified, and complex variants can be created using highly specific rules respectively.

Blueprinting provides “intelligence” for the ToyLabs Co-creation Methodology in a variety of ways, e.g. enabling optimum partner selection, creating improved toys and ensuring greater customer satisfaction, and providing increased compliance with safety and environmental regulations.

Essentially, the ToyLabs Blueprint Model is a declarative meta-model that aggregates and modularises partner, toy and technical capabilities’ data and information, by specifying two types of interrelated blueprints, used to drive the ToyLabs co-creation process: the Partner and Toy Artifact blueprints. The description of these blueprints is provided in the following paragraphs.

Partner Blueprint

The ToyLabs Partner Blueprint captures partners’ unique skills and capabilities and makes them available to potential contractors (manufacturers, FabLabs, research and technological institutes, end users etc.), assuming the role of the toy creator or inventor through the ToyLabs Collaboration Platform to help establish new co-operations for the development of new/improved toys. Focused searches for skills and capabilities among other manufacturers, fabrication laboratories and experts can then be easily performed, cultivating the grounds for the establishment of new partnerships.

Depending on the nature of entities, registered as members of the ToyLabs Community, two main types of the Partner Blueprint are foreseen and are to be developed, customising and further particularising the required types of business and technical information. These are the Partnering Organisation and Partnering Individual blueprints.

Partnering Organisation Blueprint

Regarding the organisation entities, namely manufacturers, FabLabs or experts’ and consulting companies, the Partner Blueprint combines both static information and dynamic data. The list of static elements of the Partnering Organisation Blueprint includes (not excluding unnamed elements):

- Partner Type
 - Manufacturer
 - FabLab
 - Experts’ company
- Company Contact Information
 - Company Name
 - Website/Portal

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- E-mail
- Telephone
- Fax
- Physical Address
- Service connection points (end points/URI)
- Contact Person
- Products / Services
 - Types of products produced / services offered
 - Market
 - Industry sector
- Toy Category
 - Dolls & soft-filled toys
 - Construction toys and puzzles
 - Activity toys
- Technical Competencies / Capabilities & Related Equipment Properties
 - 3D Printing
 - 3D Scanning
 - CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation
 - Circuit Production
 - CNC Milling
 - Inkjet Printing
 - Knitting Machine
 - Laser Cutting
 - Mould Casting
 - Plastic Transformation
 - Sewing Machine
 - Soldering Station
 - Vacuum Forming
 - Vinyl Cutting
- Locations and Facilities
 - Continent
 - Country
 - Region

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- Multiple sites' availability
- Certifications Awarded
 - Quality Certifications
 - Safety Certifications
- Qualifications Possessed
 - Novelty / Innovation (e.g. patents)
 - Usability
 - Durability
 - Accuracy
 - Productivity
 - Reputation
- Economic Criteria (man-hour cost, product pricelist, way of charging, etc.)
 - Man hour Cost
 - Product Pricelist
 - Way of Charging
- SLAs (SLAs framing mutual promises and covenants regarding the task / work undertaken (e.g. terms and conditions, IPR, reward, capacity / availability, etc.))

The individual criteria that specify the partners' technical competencies / capabilities and related equipment properties are defined at detail in Annex II.

Next to static entity data, the Partner Blueprint also captures and displays dynamic data that may be either pulled from a backend system (e.g., ERP) on demand and at real-time, or refreshed at regular intervals using a batch-transaction system. Dynamic elements of the Partner Blueprint include:

- Up-to-date information about current mean fabrication times
- Up-to-date information about the experts' availability

Partnering Individual Blueprint

With regard to partnering individuals, i.e. safety, environmental, childhood experts and TSIG members, the Partner Blueprint contains mainly static data. The list of static elements of the Partnering Individual Blueprint includes (not excluding unnamed elements):

- Partner Type
 - Safety Expert
 - Environmental Expert

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- Childhood Expert
- TSIG Member
- Expert Contact Information
 - Expert Name
 - E-mail
 - Telephone
 - Fax
 - Physical Address
- Location
 - Continent
 - Country
 - Region
- Area of Expertise
 - Safety
 - Quality
 - Environment
 - Children Toys
 - Electronics
- Previous Experience
- Expert Certifications
 - Safety Certifications
 - Toy Awards
- Acting as Representative of
 - Educators/Schools
 - Families
 - End users
- Costs of the Tests

For security reasons, the Partner Blueprint is instrumented in both cases with view-based mechanisms, allowing information to be selectively revealed to potential partners.

Toy Artifact Blueprint

The Toy Artifact Blueprint sets up the constraints and preconditions with respect to the creation of a toy that a partner should respond to. It can be considered as a meta-model that defines the basic concepts, necessary to assess whether a partner has the required capabilities in terms of technical equipment and skills, material and human resources to undertake a specific activity of the toy creation process.

In this respect, it helps matching partner characteristics with toy creation requirements, whereas it helps toy inventors and toy manufacturing companies to create, maintain, re-use and share core information and data around the creation of a

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

toy and make this information instantly available to any of its collaborating entities. The information contained in the Toy Artifact Blueprint enumerates the following fields:

- Toy Category
 - Dolls & soft-filled toys
 - Construction toys and puzzles
 - Activity toys
- ToyLabs Methodology Phase
 - Idea Generation & Concept Definition
 - Product Design
 - Product Development
 - Prototype Development
 - Product Engineering
 - Mould Development
 - Safety Certification
 - User Validation
- Artifact Type
 - Idea/Concept
 - Design
 - Prototype
- Artifact Version No.
- Technical Requirements
- Material Requirements
- Time and Cost Requirements
- Safety and environmental compliance requirements
- Customisation Parameters
 - Text
 - Look
 - Style
 - Other
- Related Open Issues

3.2.5.2 *Partner Selection*

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Partner Selection refers, as already suggested, to the specification of the concepts, methods and algorithms required for making comparisons among candidate partners and selecting the ones that best cover the given requirements. Partner selection is apparently a decision-making problem. As such it involves trade-offs among conflicting criteria, which in turn call upon determining the relative importance of the decision parameters. It is further a multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) problem, that requires for multiple and diverse criteria to be synthesised for potential alternatives to be prioritised by order of preference or for the best alternative to be identified. Given these characteristics, partner selection can be effectively addressed by MCDM approaches. The latter are decision support methods that allow decision makers to construct, evaluate and solve problems, associated with multiple conflicting criteria. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Analytic Network Process (ANP) and Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solutions (TOPSIS) are some well-known methods that fall under this category. These methods are briefly reviewed in the following paragraphs, to come up with the most appropriate one for addressing the partner selection problem in the context of the ToyLabs Partner Matching and Selection Methodology.

The Analytic Hierarchy Process is the most frequently used MCDM approach for partner selection in the context of supply chain management and virtual enterprises' establishment (Chai, Liu, & Ngai, 2013). Developed by Thomas Saaty in the 1970s, AHP is a technique based on pairwise comparisons, representing the relative importance of one criterion versus another (R. W. Saaty, 1987). The main benefits of the method are that it is easy and simple to use, whereas it can handle both tangible (quantitative) and intangible (qualitative) criteria.

Introduced as well by Saaty in 1996 (T. L. Saaty, 1996), the Analytic Network Process is a more advanced form of AHP, thus featuring the same basic characteristics as AHP and being thereby also appropriate for solving the partner selection problem (Sarkis, Talluri, & Gunasekaran, 2007). Still, although both approaches use pair wise comparisons to derive weights and rank alternatives, in AHP, each factor of the hierarchy structure is considered to be independent of all others, while in ANP interconnections between factors are allowed. From another point of view, ANP overcomes the issue of rank reversal, which is a well-known limitation of AHP. Nevertheless, ANP requires significantly more pairwise comparisons than AHP, which imposes an excessive burden to the decision maker.

Last but not least, TOPSIS, the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution is an MCDM technique, developed by Hwang and Yoon. TOPSIS is based on the idea that the chosen alternative should be closest to the "positive ideal solution" and the farthest from the "negative ideal solution" (Hwang, 1981). TOPSIS is characterised by great simplicity in programming, which encourages decision makers to take advantage of it; however it is capable of solely dealing with numbers and not linguistic definitions. Thereby to apply the method on qualitative criteria, additional

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

effort is required to quantify subjective terminology. TOPSIS presupposes moreover the specification of weights of objectives; thus the use of a method like AHP is still required to determine their values.

Based on the above, in view of addressing the partner selection problem in the context of the ToyLabs project, we have opted for the Analytical Hierarchy Process. The detailed description of the method is presented below.

AHP algorithmic approach

The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method is used as a means of finding the optimal solution to a complex decision problem. The application of the method involves four steps (Ansah, Sorooshian, & Bin Mustafa, 2015), as follows:

- i. the construction of the structural hierarchy
- ii. the construction of pair-wise comparison matrices
- iii. the determination of weights through a normalisation procedure
- iv. the synthesis of weights and the application of a consistency test.

In the first step of the method, the final objective of the decision problem is decomposed into a number of decision elements, which are in turn further analysed in lesser elements, until the problem acquires a hierarchical structure. The problem objective is represented at the topmost level of this structure, the criteria and sub-criteria are illustrated as the lower levels of the latter, while the potential alternatives are mapped to the lowest level of the hierarchy, as illustrated in Figure 3-4 below.

Figure 3-4. Construction of Structural Hierarchy

Once the problem structural hierarchy is constructed, the elements of each level of the hierarchy are compared in a pairwise fashion as far as the degree of importance / preference of one against the other is concerned. This comparison is realised with the help of comparison matrices, where the decision maker's preferences and judgements are declared by using a numerical scale (usually Saaty's numerical

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

gradations from 1 to 9, where 1 implies equal importance and 9 extreme importance of one element over another). A comparison matrix is mathematically represented as

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \cdots & a_{nn} \end{bmatrix}$$

where

- n represents the number of variables compared
- $a_{ij} > 0$ and $a_{ij} = \frac{1}{a_{ji}}$, where $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$

More specifically, the following apply:

- $a_{ij} > 1$, when element i is considered to be more important than element j
- $a_{ij} < 1$, when element j is considered to be more important than element i
- $a_{ij} = 1$, when an element is compared with itself ($i = j$).

Based on the above, the diagonal of the comparison matrix is equal to one, whereas the preferences granted to the rest of the matrix elements are considered to be reciprocal.

At the third step of the method, the weights of the decision elements are calculated. To this end, each value in column j is divided by the total of the values in column j . The sum of all elements' values in column j must be equal to 1, hence the values are normalised. This is represented in the equation below:

$$W = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a_{11}}{\sum a_{i1}} & \frac{a_{12}}{\sum a_{i2}} & \cdots & \frac{a_{1n}}{\sum a_{in}} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{a_{n1}}{\sum a_{i1}} & \frac{a_{n2}}{\sum a_{i2}} & \cdots & \frac{a_{nn}}{\sum a_{in}} \end{bmatrix}$$

At the last step of the method, the global weights of the alternatives are calculated through synthesis of the local weights: The normalised principal eigenvector of matrix A , also called priority vector, is obtained by averaging across the rows:

$$C = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a_{11}}{\sum a_{i1}} + \frac{a_{12}}{\sum a_{i2}} + \cdots + \frac{a_{1n}}{\sum a_{in}} \\ \cdots \\ \vdots \\ \frac{a_{n1}}{\sum a_{i1}} + \frac{a_{n2}}{\sum a_{i2}} + \cdots + \frac{a_{nn}}{\sum a_{in}} \end{bmatrix}$$

The sum of all elements in the priority vector is equal to 1. To further check the consistency of the weight values, firstly the principal eigenvalue is obtained from the

summation of products between each element of the principal eigenvector and the sum of columns of the reciprocal matrix:

$$\lambda_{max} = \begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ \vdots \\ C_n \end{bmatrix} \cdot \left[\sum a_{i1} \quad \sum a_{i2} \quad \dots \quad \sum a_{in} \right]$$

Then, the Consistency Index is calculated as follows:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1}$$

Finally, the consistency of the comparison matrix is checked by calculating the Consistency Ratio, a comparison between the Consistency Index and a Random Consistency Index.

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI}$$

The values of the Random Consistency Index are given below.

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
RI	0	0	0.58	0.9	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49

If the value of Consistency Ratio is smaller or equal to 10%, the inconsistency is acceptable. If the Consistency Ratio is greater than 10%, the decision maker needs to revise their judgment.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

4 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

This deliverable is the outcome of the coordinated effort of ToyLabs consortium, and specifically its technical partners, NTUA, SLG and AIJU, to propose a unified methodology, that will be used by the toy industry, and specifically SMEs, and will provide them with the opportunity to accelerate their innovation cycles and come up with more novel, desirable and customer-oriented toy designs, building on the power of open innovation and co-creation through the engagement of many different stakeholder types -that were not considered before- in this creative process.

In that view, a landscape analysis of selected fields of study preceded from which the state-of-the-art of these fields, their benefits as well as possible identified gaps were extracted. The selection of the research fields to be analysed was made appropriately in order to guide the methodological development for ToyLabs, in a one-to-one relationship with the different methodological aspects to be defined (i.e. sections 3.2.2-3.2.5). This literature review enabled the opportunity to better appreciate the current status of the examined research fields, find out ways to leverage them to support ToyLabs vision, as well as identify the innovation potential that arises for ToyLabs to define a completely novel and valuable methodology for the toy industry.

After acquiring useful knowledge, insights and ideas on the selected research fields, the ToyLabs methodology was defined, starting from the integrated, holistic methodology that will facilitate collaboration and co-creation among the envisioned stakeholders, and continuing with the different, discrete, but interdependent, methodologies for Market Trends Detection and Social Feedback analysis, Partner Matching and Users Feedback acquisition through Augmented Reality systems, that will act as additional modules and enablers, completing and attributing additional value to the basic methodological workflow (presented in section 3.2.2).

All methodological foundations described in section 3 respected the outcomes of the vivid discussions undertaken among consortium's partners and particularly the pilots, along with the derived requirements, documented in D1.2, in order to ensure the delivery of a methodology of value for the toy industry.

With regard to the next steps, during the next months of the project, the methodology will be denatured in concrete modules and software solutions, in the context of WP3 activities. Furthermore, an additional deliverable, D2.2, is planned for M13, that will update the work done in the context of the present deliverable and will include:

- Updates on the desk research that may emerge during these months

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- Deepening of the research on specific fields that were considered as more crucial or in need for further disambiguation (according to the feedback gathered from the application of the methodology).
- Finalisation of the integrated ToyLabs methodology and final updates on the different methodological aspects, based on the input from WP3 and WP4, regarding the design and development of the ToyLabs added-value components and integrated platform, and the pilots' experimentation, as part of WP5 activities.

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

ANNEX I: REFERENCES

- Ansah, R. H., Sorooshian, S., & Bin Mustafa, S. (2015, October). Analytic Hierarchy Process Decision Making Algorithm.
- Balcisoy, S., & Kallmann, M. (2000). A framework for rapid evaluation of prototypes with augmented reality. *Proceedings of the ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology*, 61–66. <https://doi.org/10.1145/502402.502403>
- Bayus, B. L. (2012). Crowdsourcing New Product Ideas Over Time: An Analysis of Dell's Ideastorm Community. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1979557>
- Berning, M. ., Nakazawa, J. ., Yonezawa, T. ., Beigl, M. ., Riedel, T. ., & Tokuda, H. . (2013). PARnorama: 360 Degree interactive video for augmented reality prototyping. In *UbiComp 2013 Adjunct - Adjunct Publication of the 2013 ACM Conference on Ubiquitous Computing* (pp. 1471–1474). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2494091.2499570>
- Brabham, D. C. (2008). Crowdsourcing as a Model for Problem Solving: An Introduction and Cases. *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*, 14(1), 75–90. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354856507084420>
- Budak, C., Agrawal, D., & Abbadi, A. El. (2011). Structural trend analysis for online social networks. *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment*, 646–656. <https://doi.org/10.14778/2021017.2021022>
- Busso, C., Deng, Z., Yildirim, S., Bulut, M., Lee, C. M., Kazemzadeh, A., ... Narayanan, S. (2004). Analysis of emotion recognition using facial expressions, speech and multimodal information. *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Multimodal Interfaces - ICMI '04*, 205. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1027933.1027968>
- Buyukozkan, G., & Arsenyan, J. (2012). Collaborative product development: a literature overview. *Production Planning & Control*, 23(1), 47–66. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2010.543169>
- Cha, M., Haddai, H., Benevenuto, F., & Gummadi, K. P. (2010). Measuring User Influence in Twitter : The Million Follower Fallacy. *International AAAI Conference on Weblogs and Social Media*, 10–17. <https://doi.org/10.1.1.167.192>
- Chai, J., Liu, J. N. K., & Ngai, E. W. T. (2013). Application of decision-making techniques in supplier selection: A systematic review of literature. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 40(10), 3872–3885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2012.12.040>
- Chanal, V. (2008). How to invent a new business model based on crowdsourcing : the Crowdsprite ® case How to invent a new business model based on crowdsourcing : the Crowdsprite ® case.
- Chu, V. W., Wong, R. K. K., Chen, F., & Chi, C.-H. (2014). Microblog Topic Contagiousness Measurement and Emerging Outbreak Monitoring. In

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Proceedings of the 23rd ACM International Conference on Conference on Information and Knowledge Management - CIKM '14 (pp. 1099–1108). New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2661829.2662014>

- Dang, Q., Gao, F., & Zhou, Y. (2016). Early detection method for emerging topics based on dynamic bayesian networks in micro-blogging networks. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 57(C), 285–295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2016.03.050>
- Davis, A., & Khazanchi, D. (2008, May). An Empirical Study of Online Word of Mouth as a Predictor for Multi-product Category e-Commerce Sales. *Electronic Markets*. Routledge.
- Dodgson, M., Gann, D., & Salter, A. (2006). The role of technology in the shift towards open innovation: the case of Procter & Gamble. *R and D Management*, 36(3), 333–346. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9310.2006.00429.x>
- Dueñas-Fernández, R., Velásquez, J. D., & L'Huillier, G. (2014). Detecting trends on the Web: A multidisciplinary approach. *Information Fusion*, 20, 129–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2014.01.006>
- Estelles-Arolas, E., & Gonzalez-Ladron-de-Guevara, F. (2012). Towards an integrated crowdsourcing definition. *Journal of Information Science*, 38(2), 189–200. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551512437638>
- Friedrich, W., & Friedrich, W. (2002). ARVIKA: Augmented Reality for Development, Production and Service. *The 1st International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)*, 3–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISMAR.2002.1115059>
- Fründ, J., Gausemeier, J., Matysczok, C., & Radkowski, R. (2005). Using Augmented Reality Technology to Support the Automobile Development. In *Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design* (pp. 289–298). https://doi.org/10.1007/11568421_29
- Galambos, P., Csapó, Z., Zentay, P., Fülöp, I. M., Haidegger, T., Baranyi, P., & Rudas, I. J. (2015). Design, programming and orchestration of heterogeneous manufacturing systems through VR-powered remote collaboration. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 33(C), 68–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcim.2014.08.012>
- Glance, N. S., Glance, N. S., Hurst, M., & Tomokiyo, T. (2004). BlogPulse: Automated trend discovery for weblogs. IN *WWW 2004 WORKSHOP ON THE WEBLOGGING ECOSYSTEM: AGGREGATION, ANALYSIS AND DYNAMICS*.
- Hallerstede, S. H. (2013). *Managing the Lifecycle of Open Innovation Platforms*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-02508-3>
- Han, Y., Fang, B., & Jia, Y. (2014). Predicting the topic influence trends in social media with multiple models. *Neurocomputing*, 144, 463–470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2014.03.054>
- Howe, J. (2008). Crowdsourcing: Why the Power of the Crowd Is Driving the Future of

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

Business.

- Huang, B., Yang, Y., Mahmood, A., & Wang, H. (2012). Microblog Topic Detection Based on LDA Model and Single-Pass Clustering (pp. 166–171). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-32115-3_19
- Hwang, C. L. (1981). *Multiple attribute decision making : methods and applications : a state-of-the-art survey* /. Berlin ; Springer-Verlag,.
- ISTQB. (2015). What is V-model- advantages, disadvantages and when to use it? *ISTQB Examination*, (LId).
- Jansen, B. J., & Zhang, M. (2009). Twitter power-Tweets as electronic word of mouth. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi>
- Jin, Y. S., Kim, Y. W., & Park, J. (2007). ARMO: Augmented reality based reconfigurable MOck-up. In *2007 6th IEEE and ACM International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality, ISMAR*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISMAR.2007.4538863>
- Kasiviswanathan, S. P., Melville, P., Banerjee, A., & Sindhvani, V. (2011). Emerging Topic Detection Using Dictionary Learning. In *Proceedings of the 20th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management* (pp. 745–754). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2063576.2063686>
- Kaushik, R., Apoorva Chandra, S., Mallya, D., Chaitanya, J. N. V. K., & Kamath, S. S. (2016). Sociopedia: An Interactive System for Event Detection and Trend Analysis for Twitter Data (pp. 63–70). Springer, New Delhi. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-81-322-2529-4_6
- Keller, E., & Berry, J. (2003). One American in ten tells the other nine how to vote, where to eat, and what to buy. *They Are The Influentials, New York*, 25(5), 1–8.
- Kim, H.-G., Lee, S., & Kyeong, S. (2013). Discovering hot topics using Twitter streaming data. In *Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining - ASONAM '13* (pp. 1215–1220). New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2492517.2500286>
- Klinker, G., Dutoit, A. H., Bauer, M., Bayer, J., Novak, V., & Matzke, D. (2002). Fata Morgana - A presentation system for product design. In *Proceedings - International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality, ISMAR 2002* (pp. 76–85). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISMAR.2002.1115076>
- Kontostathis, A., Galitsky, L. M., Pottenger, W. M., Roy, S., & Phelps, D. J. (2004). A Survey of Emerging Trend Detection in Textual Data Mining. *Survey of Text Mining*, 185–224. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-4305-0_9
- Lau, J., Collier, N., & Baldwin, T. (2012). On-line Trend Analysis with Topic Models: #twitter Trends Detection Topic Model Online. *International Conference on Computational Linguistics (COLING)*, 2(December), 1519–1534.
- Lee, W., & Park, J. (2006). Augmented foam: touchable and graspable augmented

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

reality for product design simulation. *Bulletin of Japanese Society for the Design Science*, 52(6), 17–26.

- Li, Y.-M., & Li, T.-Y. (2013). Deriving market intelligence from microblogs. *Decision Support Systems*, 55(1), 206–217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2013.01.023>
- Mathioudakis, M., & Koudas, N. (2010a). TwitterMonitor : Trend Detection over the Twitter Stream, 1155–1157.
- Mathioudakis, M., & Koudas, N. (2010b). TwitterMonitor: Trend Detection over the Twitter Stream. In *Proceedings of the 2010 international conference on Management of data - SIGMOD '10* (p. 1155). New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1807167.1807306>
- Mavrikios, D., Alexopoulos, K., Xanthakis, V., Pappas, M., Smparounis, K., & Chryssolouris, G. (2011). A Web-Based Platform for Collaborative Product Design, Review and Evaluation. In *Digital Factory for Human-oriented Production Systems* (pp. 35–56). London: Springer London. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-84996-172-1_3
- Nguyen, D. T., & Jung, J. E. (2017). Real-time event detection for online behavioral analysis of big social data. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 66, 137–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2016.04.012>
- Ohana, B., & Tierney, B. (2009). Sentiment Classification of Reviews Using SentiWordNet. *9th. IT & T Conference*. <https://doi.org/10.21427/D77S56>
- Pappas, M., Karabatsou, V., Mavrikios, D., & Chryssolouris, G. (2006). Development of a web-based collaboration platform for manufacturing product and process design evaluation using virtual reality techniques. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, 19(8), 805–814. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09511920600690426>
- Park, H., Moon, H. C., & Lee, J. Y. (2009). Tangible augmented prototyping of digital handheld products. *Computers in Industry*, 60(2), 114–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2008.09.001>
- Piller, F. T. (2010). Open Innovation with Customers: Crowdsourcing and Co-Creation at Threadless. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1688018>
- Piller, F. T., & Walcher, D. (2006). Toolkits for idea competitions: A novel method to integrate users in new product development. *R and D Management*, 36(3), 307–318. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9310.2006.00432.x>
- Pinto, J. C. L., Chahed, T., & Altman, E. (2015). Trend detection in social networks using Hawkes processes. In *Proceedings of the 2015 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining 2015 - ASONAM '15* (pp. 1441–1448). New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2808797.2814178>
- Pletikosa, Irena; Michahelles, F. (2011). Monitoring Trends on Facebook. *English*, 1(2).

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- Plutchik, R. (1980). A general psychoevolutionary theory of emotion. *Emotion: Theory, Research, and Experience*, 1, 3–33. <https://doi.org/citeulike-article-id:8791184>
- Re, G. M. (2013). *LOW-COST AUGMENTED REALITY FOR INDUSTRIAL PROBLEMS*. POLITECNICO DI MILANO.
- Rill, S., Reinel, D., Scheidt, J., & Zicari, R. V. (2014). PoliTwi: Early detection of emerging political topics on twitter and the impact on concept-level sentiment analysis. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 69, 24–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2014.05.008>
- Ritter, A., Mausam, Etzioni, O., & Clark, S. (2012). Open domain event extraction from twitter. In *Proceedings of the 18th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining - KDD '12* (p. 1104). New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2339530.2339704>
- Saakes, D., & Van der Lugt, R. (2007). Relight my model: new media in ideation workshops. In *Proc. Conf. Int. Association of Societies of Design Research, IASDR*.
- Saaty, R. W. (1987). The analytic hierarchy process—what it is and how it is used. *Mathematical Modelling*, 9(3–5), 161–176. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0270-0255\(87\)90473-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0270-0255(87)90473-8)
- Saaty, T. L. (1996). *Decision making with dependence and feedback: the analytic network process: the organization and prioritization of complexity*. RWS Publications.
- Saez-Trumper, D., Comarela, G., Almeida, V., Baeza-Yates, R., & Benevenuto, F. (2012). Finding trendsetters in information networks. In *Proceedings of the 18th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining - KDD '12* (p. 1014). New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2339530.2339691>
- Sankaranarayanan, J., Samet, H., Teitler, B. E., Lieberman, M. D., & Sperling, J. (2009). TwitterStand: News in Tweets. In *Proceedings of the 17th ACM SIGSPATIAL International Conference on Advances in Geographic Information Systems - GIS '09* (p. 42). New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1653771.1653781>
- Sarkis, J., Talluri, S., & Gunasekaran, A. (2007). A strategic model for agile virtual enterprise partner selection. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 27(11), 1213–1234. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443570710830601>
- Sawhney, M., Verona, G., & Prandelli, E. (2005). Collaborating to create: The Internet as a platform for customer engagement in product innovation. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 19(4), 4–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dir.20046>
- Shumaker, R., & Lackey, S. (2015). Virtual, Augmented and Mixed Reality: 7th International Conference, VAMR 2015 Held as Part of HCI International 2015 Los Angeles, CA, USA, August 2-7, 2015 Proceedings. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)* (Vol. 9179). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21067-4>

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- Sidharta, R., Oliver, J., & Sannier, A. (2006). Augmented Reality Tangible Interface for Distributed Design Review. In *Computer Graphics, Imaging and Visualisation, 2006 International Conference on* (pp. 464–470). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CGIV.2006.25>
- Stieglitz, S., & Dang-Xuan, L. (2013). Social media and political communication: a social media analytics framework. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, 3(4), 1277–1291. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13278-012-0079-3>
- Topal, B. (2015). *APPRAISAL OF AUGMENTED REALITY TECHNOLOGIES FOR SUPPORTING INDUSTRIAL DESIGN PRACTICES*. MIDDLE EAST TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY.
- Vakali, A., Giatsoglou, M., & Antaris, S. (2012). Social networking trends and dynamics detection via a cloud-based framework design. In *Proceedings of the 21st international conference companion on World Wide Web - WWW '12 Companion* (p. 1213). New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2187980.2188263>
- Verlinden, J., De Smit, A., Peeters, A. W. J., & Van Gelderen, M. H. (2003). Development of a flexible augmented prototyping system. *Journal of WSCG*, 11(3), 496–503.
- Viégas, F., Golder, S., & Donath, J. (2006). Visualizing email content: portraying relationships from conversational histories. *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 979–988. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1124772.1124919>
- Vincent Wang, X., & Xu, X. W. (2013). An interoperable solution for Cloud manufacturing. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 29(4), 232–247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcim.2013.01.005>
- Vuković, M. (2009). Crowdsourcing for enterprises. *SERVICES 2009 - 5th 2009 World Congress on Services*, (PART 1), 686–692. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SERVICES-I.2009.56>
- Wang, Y., Liu, J., Qu, J., Huang, Y., Chen, J., & Feng, X. (2014). Hashtag Graph Based Topic Model for Tweet Mining. In *2014 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining* (pp. 1025–1030). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDM.2014.60>
- Wei, F., Liu, S., Song, Y., Pan, S., Zhou X., M., Qian, W., ... Zhang, Q. (2010). TIARA: a visual exploratory text analytic system. *Kdd '10*, 153–162. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1835804.1835827>
- Wei, L., & McCallum, A. (2006). Pachinko allocation: DAG-structured mixture models of topic correlations. *ICML '06: Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Machine Learning*, (April), 577–584. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1143844.1143917>
- Wu, C. H., & Liang, W. Bin. (2011). Emotion recognition of affective speech based on multiple classifiers using acoustic-prosodic information and semantic labels. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 2(1), 10–21. <https://doi.org/10.1109/T-AFFC.2010.16>

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

- Yongtao Ye, Yajun Du, & Xia Fu. (2016). Hot topic extraction based on Chinese Microblog's Features topic model. In *2016 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing and Big Data Analysis (ICCCBDA)* (pp. 348–353). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCBDA.2016.7529582>
- Zanzotto, F. M., Pennacchiotti, M., & Tsioutsoulouklis, K. (2011). Linguistic Redundancy in Twitter. In *Proc. of the 2011 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, ACL* (pp. 659–669).
- Zha, X., & Sriram, R. D. (2004). Collaborative Product Development and Customization: A Platform-based Strategy and Implementation.
- Zhang, X., Chen, X., Chen, Y., Wang, S., Li, Z., & Xia, J. (2015). Event detection and popularity prediction in microblogging. *Neurocomputing*, *149*, 1469–1480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2014.08.045>
- Zhou, D., Chen, L., & He, Y. (2015). An Unsupervised Framework of Exploring Events on Twitter: Filtering, Extraction and Categorization. *Twenty-Ninth AAAI Conference on Artificial ...*, 2468–2474.
- Zhu, T., & Yu, J. (2014). A Prerecognition Model for Hot Topic Discovery Based on Microblogging Data. *The Scientific World Journal*, *2014*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/360934>

ANNEX II: PARTNER SELECTION TECHNICAL CRITERIA

Table 0-1 Technical criteria related to 3D Printing

3D Printing			
<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Unit of Measurement (if applicable)</i>	<i>Alternatives</i>	<i>Toy Creation Activity</i>
type of 3D printer		e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •FDM (Fused Deposition Modelling) printer •Laser sintering •3D inkjet printer 	Prototype development
printer resolution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Layer thickness •X-Y resolution 	range in dpi or μm	accepted range: 0.1 mm	
compatible/supported data formats		e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •STL (Stereolithography) •AMF (Additive Manufacturing File format) •3MF 	
supported materials		e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •plastics, additives, resins •paper and cardboard •electric and electronic components •metal •wood and derivatives •textile 	

Table 0-2 Technical criteria related to 3D Scanning

3D Scanning			
<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Unit of Measurement (if applicable)</i>	<i>Alternatives</i>	<i>Toy Creation Activity</i>
3D scanner resolution/accuracy	in mm		Product design

Table 0-3 Technical criteria related to Circuit Production

Circuit Production			
<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Unit of Measurement (if applicable)</i>	<i>Alternatives</i>	<i>Toy Creation Activity</i>

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

PBC creation			Prototype development
Elements assembly			
Elements test			
Elements selection			

Table 0-4 Technical criteria related to CNC Milling

CNC Milling			
Criteria	Unit of Measurement (if applicable)	Alternatives	Toy Creation Activity
type of milling cutter			?
CNC software available			
milling precision			
milling speed			

Table 0-5 Technical criteria related to Inkjet Printing

Inkjet Printing			
Criteria	Unit of Measurement (if applicable)	Alternatives	Toy Creation Activity
cost			Product development
productivity			
time			

Table 0-6 Technical criteria related to Knitting Machine

Knitting Machine			
Criteria	Unit of Measurement (if applicable)	Alternatives	Toy Creation Activity
finishing			Prototype development
knitting speed			

Table 0-7 Technical criteria related to Laser Cutting

Laser Cutting			
Criteria	Unit of Measurement (if applicable)	Alternatives	Toy Creation Activity
type of laser		e.g. •CO2 laser •Nd/ Nd-YAG laser	?
precision (wavelength or focal length of the laser beam)	range in mm		
method of laser cutting		e.g. •vaporization •melt and blow •thermal stress cracking	
sheet thickness	in mm		

Project ID ...	ToyLabs
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1

laser power	in KWh		
cutting speed	in meters per minute		
supported materials		e.g. •plastics, additives, resins •paper and cardboard •electric and electronic components •metal •wood and derivatives •textile	

Table 0-8 Technical criteria related to Mould Casting

Mould Casting			
Criteria	Unit of Measurement (if applicable)	Alternatives	Toy Creation Activity
accuracy (of mould finishing)			Mould development, Product development
supported materials (mixture of metals)			
production time			
productivity			
vacuum casting size		1000*1000mm from master model/sculpt	
materials cost			

Table 0-9 Technical criteria related to Sewing Machine

Sewing Machine			
Criteria	Unit of Measurement (if applicable)	Alternatives	Toy Creation Activity
employee experience			(Prototype creation)
equipment			

Table 0-10 Technical criteria related to Soldering Station

Soldering Station			
Criteria	Unit of Measurement (if applicable)	Alternatives	Toy Creation Activity
metal alloys		1mm	?

Table 0-11 Technical criteria related to Vacuum Forming

Vacuum Forming

Project ID ...	ToyLabs	
Date: 2017-07-17	Deliverable D2.1	

<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Unit of Measurement (if applicable)</i>	<i>Alternatives</i>	<i>Toy Creation Activity</i>
cost			Product development
productivity			
time			

Table 0-12 Technical criteria related to Vinyl Cutting

Vinyl Cutting			
<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Unit of Measurement (if applicable)</i>	<i>Alternatives</i>	<i>Toy Creation Activity</i>
precision			Prototype development, Product development
experience			
cost			
productivity			
time			